

Master Thesis

Exploring motivating factors for soil protection measures by farmers in the Spanish region of Guadalajara: A Q-Methodology approach

submitted by

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This thesis is dedicated to Pedro Lunar and Yaritza Gonzalez.

Affidavit

I hereby declare that I have authored this master thesis independently, and that I have not used any assistance other than that which is permitted. The work contained herein is my own except where explicitly stated otherwise. All ideas taken in wording or in basic content from unpublished sources or from published literature, as well as those which were generated using artificial intelligence tools, are duly identified and cited, and the precise references included.

I further declare that this master thesis has not been submitted, in whole or in part, in the same or a similar form, to any other educational institution as part of the requirements for an academic degree.

I hereby confirm that I am familiar with the standards of Scientific Integrity and with the guidelines of Good Scientific Practice, and that this work fully complies with these standards and guidelines.

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Table of content

Affidavit	ii
Acknowledgements.....	iii
Table of content	iv
Abstract.....	vi
Kurzfassung	vii
1. Introduction	1
2. Background Information	4
2.1. Climate Extremes and their impact on arable land	4
2.2. Soil conditions, their management and significance	5
2.3. Functioning of the Common Agricultural Policy of the EU	7
2.4. Guadalajara	10
2.5. Influences	13
3. State of the Art	16
3.1. Dispositional factors	16
3.2. Social Factors.....	17
3.3. Cognitive Factors	19
4. The Q-Methodology	21
4.1. The Q-Set	22
4.2. The Questionnaire.....	25
4.3. Interview Procedure – The Q-Sort	25
4.4. Ethical consent	27
4.5. The P-Set	27
4.6. Q-Analysis	29
4.7. Time contextualization of the Interviews.....	30
5. Results	32
5.1. The Guadalajarean farmer	32
5.2. Statistical Analysis	34

5.3.	Similarities Across the Archetypes	40
5.4.	Archetypes	41
6.	Discussion.....	49
6.1.	What unites the farmers of Guadalajara	49
6.2.	Archetypal Farmers and the factors shaping their decisions.....	50
6.3.	Policy Conclusions	53
6.4.	Study Limitations	54
7.	Conclusions.....	56
8.	References	59
	Declaration of the use of generative AI tools	72
	List of Abbreviation.....	74
	List of Figures.....	75
	List of Tables.....	76
	Appendix A: Spanish Statements.....	77
	Appendix B: Questionnaire (Spanish)	79
	Appendix C: Consent Form (Spanish)	81
	Appendix D: General Participants Information sheet (english).....	84
	Appendix E: Participants Information sheet (Spain Version).....	87
	Appendix F: Interview Protocol (Spanish)	90

Abstract

Soil health is crucial for agricultural productivity and environmental sustainability, yet farmers' adoption of soil protection practices varies widely. This study focuses on understanding the motivations behind soil management decisions among farmers in Guadalajara, Spain, using the Q-methodology. The research identifies three archetypes of farmers: "*The Soil Considered*," who prioritize long-term soil health; "*The Economic Individualist*," who focuses on immediate economic gains; and "*The Contemporary Minded*," who balance economic viability with ecological responsibility. Through semi-structured interviews and Q-sorting, the study reveals that economic pressures, skepticism towards external advice, and bureaucratic challenges are significant barriers to adopting sustainable practices. The findings suggest that current policy measures, particularly those related to the Common Agricultural Policy, are inadequate in addressing these challenges. Farmers expressed a preference for compensation in addition to fair market prices rather than traditional subsidies. The study concludes that a wider approach in agricultural policies, which includes expanding Agri-Environmental Schemes and reducing bureaucratic burdens, could better support soil conservation efforts. This research provides valuable insights for policymakers aiming to enhance agricultural resilience and sustainability, though further investigation is needed to address the economic and social barriers hindering broader adoption of sustainable practices.

Kurzfassung

Die Bodengesundheit ist für die landwirtschaftliche Produktivität und die ökologische Nachhaltigkeit von entscheidender Bedeutung. Dennoch wenden Landwirte sehr unterschiedliche Bodenschutzmaßnahmen an. Diese Arbeit konzentriert sich darauf, die Beweggründe von Landwirten in Guadalajara, Spanien, für ihre Bodenbewirtschaftungsentscheidungen mit Hilfe der Q-Methode zu verstehen. Dabei wurden drei Archetypen von Landwirten identifiziert: "*The Soil Considered*", welcher der langfristigen Bodengesundheit Priorität einräumt, "*The Economic Individualist*", der sich auf kurzfristige ökonomische Gewinne konzentriert, und "*The Contemporary Minded*", welcher ein Gleichgewicht zwischen ökonomischer Rentabilität und ökologischer Verantwortung anstrebt. Mit Hilfe von halbstrukturierten Interviews und Q-Sorting zeigt diese Arbeit, dass wirtschaftlicher Druck sowie Skepsis gegenüber externen Empfehlungen und bürokratischen Herausforderungen erhebliche Hindernisse für die Einführung nachhaltiger Strategien darstellen. Die Ergebnisse deuten darauf hin, dass die derzeitigen politischen Maßnahmen, insbesondere im Rahmen der Gemeinsamen Agrarpolitik, nicht ausreichen um diesen Herausforderungen zu begegnen. Die Landwirte sprachen sich für fairen Ausgleichszahlungen aus. Das Fazit der Arbeit zeigt, dass ein umfassenderer agrarpolitischer Ansatz, der eine Ausweitung der Agrarumweltprogramme und eine Verringerung des bürokratischen Aufwands beinhaltet, die Bemühungen um den Bodenschutz besser unterstützen könnte. Diese Arbeit liefert Erkenntnisse für politische Entscheidungsträger, die die Nachhaltigkeit der Landwirtschaft verbessern wollen. Weitere Untersuchungen sind jedoch erforderlich, um die wirtschaftlichen und sozialen Hindernisse zu beseitigen, die einer breiteren Einführung nachhaltiger Praktiken entgegenstehen.

1. Introduction

The health of soil is fundamental to agricultural productivity and essential for global food security, directly influencing the capacity of agricultural systems to support the world's population. Soil degradation poses a threat to agricultural sustainability, manifesting through processes such as erosion, nutrient depletion, and contamination (Stahr *et al.*, 2020). This threat could be further worsened by the advancing impacts of climate change, as highlighted by the findings of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) in 2018. The IPCC report draws attention to the increased frequency and severity of extreme weather events, such as floods and droughts, which compromise soil integrity and, by extension, the viability of agricultural practices. Furthermore, traditional farming techniques often intensify the vulnerability of soil to erosion, a natural geomorphic process that, when accelerated by human activities, results in significant and long-lasting damage to soil health and its capacity to support crop growth (Boardman *et al.*, 2003; Govers *et al.*, 2004). This phenomenon is illustrated in regions like the semi-arid areas of Guadalajara, Spain, where aggressive agricultural practices have led to notable decreases in soil carbon storage and biodiversity (Hontoria Fernández *et al.*, 2004; Alvarez-Uria *et al.*, 2012; Albaladejo *et al.*, 2013).

Understanding the impact of soil management on soil degradation is a complex challenge, influenced by numerous factors. These include the land's physical characteristics (Lapple & Kelley, 2015), the goals and motivation of individual farmers (Karali *et al.*, 2014; Dessart *et al.*, 2019; Braitto *et al.*, 2020), and the broader social and institutional frameworks (Githinji *et al.*, 2023), all of which can either contribute to or mitigate soil degradation. The health of the soil and their management extends far-reaching implications beyond just agricultural yields. It plays a crucial role in the sustainability of ecosystems, the availability of resources and the well-being of communities (Alori *et al.*, 2020; Neher *et al.*, 2022). It is within this context that farmers are recognized not only as beneficiaries of healthy soil but also as its stewards (Panagos *et al.*, 2016). Their actions and decisions are essential in conserving soil quality and, consequently, ensuring the longevity and productivity of their lands (Serebrennikov *et al.*, 2020). Cooperative efforts are vital for enhancing agricultural resilience and adaptability in the face of uncertainties like climate change and market fluctuations (Mills *et al.*, 2017).

For an effective implementation of soil protection strategies, it is important to understand the motivations that determine farmers' behaviour. There is often a discrepancy between the soil conservation methods recommended by scientists and the practices actually used by farmers, a discrepancy that is due to a variety of factors, including economic, social and personal considerations (Braitto *et al.*, 2020). The decision-making process in agriculture is influenced by a complex web of factors. Factors such as personal beliefs, age, level of education, attitudes, social norms, and values play a significant role, as does a broader understanding of the relationship between humans and nature (Mills *et al.*, 2017; Bartkowski & Bartke, 2018; Serebrennikov *et al.*, 2020; Braitto *et al.*, 2020). Farmers, due to their intimate connection with

the land, often embody a unique perspective on interacting with nature, which differentiates them from the wider population (Baldwin *et al.*, 2017). Adopting conservation practices, such as preserving native vegetation, is often a reflection of a deep emotional connection to the land, signifying an inherent respect for the natural world (Gosling & Williams, 2010). Understanding agricultural behavior also requires to consider the business-oriented aspects of farming, which entail significant personal and economic investments and commitments (Dessart *et al.*, 2019). Identifying the motivational drivers behind farmers' willingness or reluctance to adopt soil conservation measures is critical for developing effective environmental policies and encouraging sustainable agricultural practices. This study aims to address existing research gaps by focusing on a region that has not been yet extensively explored in the literature. Although much has been written about the factors influencing farmers' decision, no research has been found specific to this area, Guadalajara (Spain). The use of the Q-Methodology in this study provides valuable insights by combining both quantitative and through interviews gathered qualitative data, offering a more nuanced perspective for decision making.

This study does this in the context of the *SoilX* project. *SoilX* is a comprehensive investigation into the motivational factors driving soil conservation practices among farmers in Europe. Building on the work of Braitto *et al.* (2020) this study categorizes different viewpoints into distinct groups, and so offering a deeper understanding of the motivations that drive soil conservation efforts among farmers. The aim is to shed light on the complexities of agricultural decision-making and contribute to the formulation of strategies that foster sustainable farming practices, ensuring the long-term health and productivity of the soil. This leads to the main research question for this thesis:

1. *Which archetypal viewpoints on soil management can be identified and what key factors influence farmers in Guadalajara, Spain, when choosing their soil management methods?*

Based on the results of this question, the following additional questions can be formulated to help further refine the image of the guadalajarean farmer and to draw conclusions.

a. *Which challenges prevent farmers from adopting practices that favor soil health?*

b. *What conclusions can be drawn regarding current policy measures and how can they be improved to better support sustainable practices?*

A broad literature explores the perspectives of different farming groups, identifying recurring viewpoints and typologies. Bartkowski's *et al.* (2022) review highlights that the most common type is the *Productivist*, characterized by a strong emphasis on food production and an economic focus, often practicing intensive agriculture. This group is often described as having limited awareness of climate change (Cullen *et al.*, 2020). Other common types include the *Innovator*, who is open to adopting and experimenting with new

approaches and practices; the *Diversifier*, who is not solely focused on food production but expands their portfolio, often sharing traits with the *Innovator*; and the *Traditionalist*, who is conservative and resistant to change. *Traditionalists* are often aware of environmental issues but may be unwilling or unable to adapt their practices (Bartkowski *et al.*, 2022). The *Environmentalist* is another common type. They have a close relationship with nature and show concern for the environment in their farming practices and are keen to improve their soil management (Braitto *et al.*, 2020; Bartkowski *et al.*, 2022).

The remainder of this thesis is structured as follows:

First, Chapter 2 provides essential *background information* on climate extremes and their impact on arable land. It also examines different agricultural management styles and the general workings of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). Additionally, this chapter offers detailed information about the region of Guadalajara, setting the context for the study. Chapter 3 presents the *state of research* on farmers' behavior. In this chapter, I review the current literature and existing studies relevant to the motivational factors influencing soil conservation practices among farmers. Chapter 4, *Methods*, explains the Q-Methodology used in this thesis. The Methods chapter describes the Q-Methodology used in detail and also explains the reasons for choosing this method and points out its suitability for investigating the research questions. Chapter 5 presents the *results* of the study, showcasing the findings obtained from applying the Q-Methodology among farmers in the Guadalajara region. This chapter provides a detailed analysis of the data collected. Chapter 6 *discusses* the results in detail, interpreting the findings in the context of the existing literature and explaining their implications for soil protection practice and policy. Through this, a deeper understanding of the results is provided, and their significance analyzed. The final chapter *Conclusion*, Chapter 7, summarizes the key findings of this study, discusses its limitations, and provides recommendations for future research and practical applications.

2. Background Information

In this chapter, I will explore various factors that have an influence the outcome of this study. Climate extremes and their impacts play a significant role in soil health, as do the different soil management practices, which I will discuss in detail. Additionally, the European Union's subsidy system, with its complex structure, has a major influence on decision-making, so I will explain its various pillars and provide context. Understanding the geographical setting of this research-site is equally important; therefore, I will also provide an overview of the guadalajarean region, where the interviews for this thesis were conducted.

2.1. Climate Extremes and their impact on arable land

In Europe, the landscape of extreme weather events is transforming significantly, with an increase in both severe summer droughts and intense, though less frequent, rainfall episodes. These events, as characterized by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (Field & Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2012), represent anomalies in weather patterns that push beyond the normal range of observed conditions. This includes sudden, short-lived occurrences like heavy rainfall during storms, as well as prolonged heatwaves linked to droughts (IPCC, 2023). For farmers, the impacts are particularly harsh, leading to drought-induced plant stress, erosion, and significant reductions in agricultural yield (Cogato *et al.*, 2019; Ouda & Zohry, 2022). According to projections from recent IPCC reports, Europe is going to experience an rise in temperature extremes, correlating with a rise in evapotranspiration and decreased rainfall, both contributing factors to drought conditions (Field & Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2012; Van Loon, 2015). These changes align with global warming scenarios outlined in the Paris Agreement, which anticipates an increase in the number of heat days under a 2 degrees Celsius warming scenario (UNFCCC, 2016).

Research categorizes droughts into various types — meteorological, hydrological, and agricultural — each defined by specific criteria. Drucap and his team define droughts as “*a lack of rainfall so great and long continued as to affect injuriously the plant and animal life of a place and to deplete water supplies both for domestic purposes and for the operation of power plants, especially in those regions where rainfall is normally sufficient for such purpose*” (Dracup *et al.*, 1980). Agricultural droughts, which focus on the impact of water shortages on crop yields, consider both meteorological conditions and soil moisture levels (Vicente-Serrano *et al.*, 2010; Brunner, 2023).

The definition of heavy precipitation often varies, as it is defined by regional or percentage indicators to characterize its severity (Alexander *et al.*, 2006; Groisman *et al.*, 2013). In a nutshell, increasing global temperatures enhance atmospheric water vapor capacity, intensifying the hydrological cycle and

increasing the likelihood of severe rainfall events and floods (Westra *et al.*, 2014; Breugem *et al.*, 2020; Emmanouil *et al.*, 2022). In agriculture, extreme precipitation can lead to significant water erosion, stripping away nutrient-rich topsoil and reducing overall soil fertility (Martín-Velázquez *et al.*, 2022). This risk intensifies when droughts are followed by heavy rains, as dry soils have diminished capacity to absorb water (Corominas & Moya, 1999).

The interplay between droughts and heavy precipitation is expected to become more common, posing increased risks to soil health and agricultural productivity (IPCC, 2023). The effectiveness of mitigation and management strategies against these impacts will significantly depend on both physical soil properties and agricultural practices, topics that will be further explored in subsequent sections (UNFCCC, 2016; Page *et al.*, 2020).

2.2. Soil conditions, their management and significance

Healthy soils, described by their resilience, are able to adapt to and recover from environmental stresses while supporting a robust biota (Lehman *et al.*, 2015). In an agricultural context, the functional properties of healthy soil include the provision of nutrients, disease control, production of growth factors, water availability and reduction of erosion (Hesterberg, 1998; Stahr *et al.*, 2020). The implementation of effective mitigation and adaptation strategies is crucial to minimize the risks posed by these extreme weather conditions (Lorenzo *et al.*, 2016).

In regions such as Guadalajara, where agricultural practices are resource-intensive due to the continental climate and nutrient-poor soils, the impact of intensive agriculture on soil health is substantial. The excessive use of soil results in a decline in biodiversity, including important organisms such as earthworms (Butchart *et al.*, 2010), and significantly degrades overall soil health (Cárceles Rodríguez *et al.*, 2022). Intensive soil management practices, including the use of heavy machinery, contribute to soil compaction and lead to a range of physical, chemical, and biological degradations, including erosion and organic matter decomposition (Bünemann *et al.*, 2018; Cárceles Rodríguez *et al.*, 2022). Short-term remedies, such as over-fertilization and intensive ploughing, may temporarily enhance soil conditions, although lead to long-term negative impacts on soil health and so creating a damaging cycle (Henneron *et al.*, 2015)

The adoption of sustainable farming practices offers a strategic way to reverse this damaging cycle of declining soil quality (Henneron *et al.*, 2015; Bünemann *et al.*, 2018). Optimizing soil management practices to improve soil health and structure is crucial for strengthening the resilience of agriculture to extreme weather events and so reducing the associated risks in crop production (Cogato *et al.*, 2019). Such a strategic approach does not only ensure long-term sustainability, but also supports the overall efficiency and productivity of agricultural systems (Ogle *et al.*, 2005). In the following paragraphs, I examine some of

the effects of different types of work on the soil. From conventional agricultural activities such as ploughing to sustainable methods that can improve soil health.

2.2.1. Conventional agricultural Methods

Mechanical soil preparation or mechanical ploughing is one of the classic conventional methods of agriculture. Ploughing is used for various reasons such as weed control, seedbed preparation and short-term improvement of soil structure and aeration (Wasaya *et al.*, 2019). Turning or breaking up the soil buries weeds and their seeds deep under the soil, which inhibits their growth, and loosening increases aeration and promotes root growth and water infiltration (Šarauskis *et al.*, 2018). However, ploughing often makes the soil more vulnerable to erosion, which can lead to a loss of the top and most fertile soil layer (Edeso *et al.*, 1999). Ploughing also exposes the organic material in the soil to more air, which leads to faster oxidation and thus to a loss of soil organic matter (Arya *et al.*, 2020). This disrupts the natural habitat of many soil organisms, which in turn can lead to a decline in biodiversity in the soil (Lal, 2009).

In addition to the use of heavy machinery, the use of chemical inputs is a key element of conventional agriculture. For example, chemical fertilizers are used which, although they enable faster growth, can also lead to soil acidification, a reduction in organic matter and the disruption of natural nutrient cycles (Alori *et al.*, 2020). The use of pesticides, herbicides and fungicides can also lead to a decline in microbial diversity in the soil and disturb natural biological processes that are crucial for maintaining a healthy soil structure (Hartmann *et al.*, 2015).

2.2.2. Reduced Soil Management and No-Till

Reduced tillage is an agricultural practice in which the aim is to minimize soil disturbance. This involves using equipment that digs less deeply into the soil than conventional ploughing or only slightly disturbs the soil surface, such as grubber (Berner *et al.*, 2008). These measures lead to an increase in soil organic matter, which in turn can lead to improved biological soil activity (Berner *et al.*, 2008; Gadermaier *et al.*, 2012).

In the case of direct sowing without tillage, in other words no-till, there is no ploughing at all, and the seeds are sown directly on the previous crop residues. An important component is the maintenance of a permanent soil cover by the crop residues (Triplett & Dick, 2008). This mulch layer protects the soil from erosion and promotes moisture retention (Obour *et al.*, 2021).

Both methods significantly reduce soil erosion and thus protect fertile soil. They also increase the infiltration rate and water storage in the soil, making it more drought-resistant (Berner *et al.*, 2008;

Henneron *et al.*, 2015). Due to the increased organic matter in both practices, soils managed with no-till or reduced tillage act as carbon sinks and help counteract the climate crisis (Stahr *et al.*, 2020).

Nevertheless, these two methods also raise some problems. Due to the lack of ploughing, weed management can become more difficult and more herbicides have to be used, which in some cases can lead to resistance problems (Jayaraman & Dalal, 2022). Pest and disease pressure can also arise if crop residues are left in the fields. And importantly for farmers, in some cases yields may only stabilize or improve after years of transition (Jayaraman *et al.*, 2021; Jayaraman & Dalal, 2022).

2.2.3. Cover crops and Crop rotation

Cover crops are plants that are grown primarily to benefit the soil rather than to increase crop yield. They improve soil structure by breaking up compacted layers, increasing porosity and promoting the infiltration of nutrients and water (Wittwer *et al.*, 2017). Legumes such as clover can fix atmospheric nitrogen and enrich the soil (Carr *et al.*, 2013). They prevent soil erosion by covering the soil when primary crops are not present, reduce weed germination by blocking sunlight, and increase biodiversity by attracting beneficial insects and promoting a balanced ecosystem (Wittwer *et al.*, 2017). However, they may not be practical in regions with severe water shortages, extremely short growing seasons, or in regions where the costs of managing cover crops exceed the benefits (Wittwer *et al.*, 2017; Obour *et al.*, 2021). Some robust cover crops can be difficult to eradicate and require additional labor or herbicide application, while in dry regions, they can compete with main crops for water (Carr *et al.*, 2013).

Crop rotation is particularly important in areas where intensive farming is conducted and the risk of soil depletion is higher (Karlen *et al.*, 1994). In crop rotation, plants of different species are grown on the same field at recurring intervals. This rotation can be annual or seasonal and depends on the specific requirements of the crops. Often legumes, in other words plants that can store atmospheric nitrogen by forming nodules in symbiosis with rhizobia, are integrated in order to enrich the soil with nitrogen in a natural way (Karlen *et al.*, 1994; Stahr *et al.*, 2020). As many pests and diseases are specifically adapted to crops, the rotation reduces their ability to spread quickly and easily (Selim, 2019). However, a well-functioning crop rotation requires careful planning and restricts farmers, as some crops that are well suited to crop rotation may not be economically lucrative (Selim, 2019).

2.3. Functioning of the Common Agricultural Policy of the EU

The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) of the European Union is a central element of EU policy that has significantly shaped agriculture within the member states since its introduction in 1962 (Burrell, 2009). After the Second World War, Europe faced serious supply problems in the agricultural sector, mainly due

to food shortages. The CAP was intended not only to increase food production, but also to ensure a fair and equal income for farmers and thus strengthen the economy in rural areas (Guth *et al.*, 2020). Over the years, the CAP has been reformed several times to respond to new challenges such as environmental concerns, overproduction and the need to integrate new Member States (Stępień & Czyżewski, 2019).

2.3.1. Funding

The funding of the CAP is a complex and dynamic system based on the EU budget. This budget is fed by contributions from the Member States, which are determined according to their economic performance. The allocation of funds between the two pillars of the CAP - direct payments and rural development - is flexible and is adjusted according to the respective needs and political priorities of the EU and its member states (European Commission, 2022).

The first pillar of the CAP primarily comprises direct payments to farmers and market regulation measures. These are of central importance as they directly stabilize farmers' incomes and make them predictable to a certain extent. This pillar is financed by the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF) (European Commission, n.d.). A key feature of direct payments is the link to so-called cross-compliance criteria, which ensure that subsidies are linked to compliance with certain environmental, health and animal welfare standards (European Commission, 2022). Market measures within the first pillar aim to guarantee price stability for agricultural products. This is achieved, for example, through the purchase and storage of surpluses or the granting of export subsidies to increase the competitiveness of European products on the world market (European Commission, n.d.).

The second pillar of the CAP is dedicated to the development of rural areas and is financed by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) (European Commission, n.d.). The focus here is on increasing the competitiveness of agriculture, protecting the environment and improving the quality of life in rural areas. Supporting environmentally friendly farming practices, promoting young farmers and diversifying the rural economy are core measures under this pillar (European Commission, 2019).

The CAP has recently introduced numerous instruments designed to strengthen environmental protection. Nevertheless, there is a broad consensus that the current measures are not yet sufficient to effectively address ongoing environmental degradation and the challenges of climate change (Pe'er *et al.*, 2019; Pe'er & Lakner, 2020; European Court of Auditors., 2021; Ruby Silk, 2022; Cuadros-Casanova *et al.*, 2023). CAP expenditure accounts for around 33% of the total EU budget, which is equivalent around 58 billion euros in 2020 (European Commission, 2020a). The vast majority of this expenditure takes the form of direct payments to farmers. This two-part structure of the CAP allows a wide range of objectives to be pursued. Nevertheless, the efficiency and appropriateness of the

distribution of these funds remains a central point of discussion when it comes to the future organization and further development of the CAP.

2.3.2. Subsidies

The application for subsidies within the framework CAP is governed by a formalized process coordinated by national authorities in the EU Member States. This process requires farmers to register their farms with the responsible national authority and complete extensive application documents. This documentation is crucial to assess eligibility for direct payments and other support programs. (European Commission, 2023)

As part of the application process, farmers are required to provide detailed information about the nature of their farms. This includes information on the size and utilization of the farmed land, the type of farming practiced, and the agricultural techniques implemented. The data collected is used to evaluate the entitlement to specific subsidies (European Commission, 2019). Evaluation criteria include a wide range of indicators of environmental protection, animal welfare and the promotion of rural development (Europäischer Rat, 2024).

The amount of subsidies allocated varies significantly between the Member States and the specific support programs. The subsidy amounts can vary depending on the type of farm and regional circumstances (Střeleček *et al.*, 2009). For Spain the CAP-Budget for 2023 amounts to approximately 34 billion euros with 76% going to the first pillar and 24% going the second pillar (Nadeu *et al.*, 2023). Of the 76% in the first pillar, however, 20% is attributable to eco-schemes, as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Spanish Budget allocation to interventions in Pillar 1 and Pillar 2 (Nadeu *et al.*, 2023)

Despite the financial security that CAP subsidies provide for many farms, there are also critical voices regarding the distribution of funds. Research suggests that payments are often favoring larger, more

productive farms, to the disadvantage of smaller or less efficient farms (Pe'er *et al.*, 2019; Guth *et al.*, 2020). This disparity can lead to inequalities within the agricultural community and jeopardizes the effectiveness of the CAP, particularly with regard to its environmental and social policy objectives.

2.4. Guadalajara

Guadalajara is a city in the province of Guadalajara. Guadalajara (the city) is also the capital of the autonomous community of Castilla la Mancha. Located approximately one hour northeast of Madrid, it holds the status of provincial capital, making it the center for all administrative functions of the province, encompassing both regional and provincial government activities. Additionally, the Spanish government maintains a sub-delegation in Guadalajara, which operates under the authority of the government delegate for the autonomous community, with its headquarters in Toledo. In the European Union's official statistics framework (Eurostat, 2024), the region analyzed for this work falls within the ES 42 region (Castilla la Mancha) at the NUTS 2 level, and more specifically, it is situated in the ES424 area (Guadalajara) at the NUTS 3 level.

Agriculture in Guadalajara has undergone significant change, particularly as a result of urban and industrial development around Madrid, which has led to a rapid loss of fertile soil (García-Quintana *et al.*, 2004). This change is attributed to new models of local and regional development that emphasize a shift from traditional agricultural practices to more urban-based economic activities. The critical analysis of soil sealing using LANDSAT images over a 15-year period illustrates this change and shows a significant decrease in agricultural land, mainly due to urban sprawl and industrial expansion (García Rodríguez & Pérez González, 2007).

The weather in Guadalajara, which is characterized by its Mediterranean influence, has changed, notably due to climate crisis-related changes, which have had an impact on agricultural practices (Peña-Gallardo *et al.*, 2019). The political landscape of Guadalajara has also been subject to change, particularly in relation to land management and environmental policy.

2.4.1. Geology and Topography

The majority of Guadalajara, including the city itself, is situated within the *Alcarria*, a plateau characterized by its tabular relief. This area is primarily elevated at around 1000 meters above sea level. The geological foundation of the Alcarria region is comprised of quartzite conglomerates and limestone, which contribute to the formation of poor and arid lands (García Rodríguez & Pérez González, 2007). These geological formations result in a landscape with limited soil fertility, affecting agricultural productivity and vegetation types. Transitioning from the upland to the river Henares, the landscape transforms into an escarpment with an average slope of 20% (Arribas *et al.*, 2000). This area,

along with the neighboring glacis, is primarily composed of marl and shale. These geological materials influence soil composition and stability, affecting erosion rates and soil moisture retention (Sancho Comins *et al.*, 1993). The glacis areas in particular, tend to be where population centers are established, benefiting from the slightly more fertile soils and gentler topography compared to the steep escarpment (Arribas *et al.*, 2000). Contrasting with the *Alcarria* and its slopes, the westernmost part of Guadalajara and the exclave of *Usanos* lie at elevations below 700 meters above sea level, on the right bank of the river *Henares* (Serrano, 1985). This segment of the province is part of the *Henares valley*, featuring flatter terrains with gentler slopes. The soils here are predominantly composed of sandy clays near the river, suitable for irrigation and thus more agriculturally productive (Serrano, 1985). Between *Marchamalo* and *Usanos*, *arkoses* dominate, indicating a sedimentary environment with significant contributions from weathered granite, which can influence soil texture and fertility (García Rodríguez & Pérez González, 2007).

The variation in elevation and geological substrates across Guadalajara influences water availability, with the *Henares valley* offering more opportunities for irrigation and water retention due to its flatter terrain and the presence of the river (Arribas *et al.*, 2000). In contrast, the higher elevations of the *Alcarria*, with their conglomerates and limestone, present challenges for water conservation and agricultural irrigation, reflecting a need for sustainable water management practices in these areas (Sancho Comins *et al.*, 1993; García Rodríguez & Pérez González, 2007).

2.4.2. Temperatures

Guadalajara is characterized by a distinct continental Mediterranean climate due to its central peninsular location and considerable distance from the sea. This geographic positioning influences the area's rainfall patterns and thermal regime, resulting in moderate precipitation levels and pronounced daily and seasonal temperature fluctuations (Archilla *et al.*, 1989). According to the Köppen climate classification, Guadalajara falls under the Csa category, typical of a Mediterranean climate with specific continental influences (Köppen, 1923). This classification denotes regions with a temperate warm climate where the driest month in summer has less than 30 mm of precipitation and less than one-third of the precipitation of the wettest month in winter (Miller, 2019). The summers in Guadalajara are long, dry, and hot. During this period, the region experiences a marked decrease in rainfall, with average precipitation levels dropping to approximately 20-30 mm per month, compared to the annual average of 400-600 mm (Archilla *et al.*, 1989). Simultaneously, temperatures often rise significantly, reaching average highs of 35°C in August of 2023 (Agencia Estatal de Meteorología, 2023). These climatic conditions can lead to increased evapotranspiration rates and water stress for local agriculture, which favours the cultivation of warm-weather crops, but also puts pressure on water resources and increases the risk of forest fires (Stahr *et al.*, 2020). In contrast, winters are equally

extended and noted for their harshness. The temperatures can drop below freezing, resulting in frost formation and occasional snowfall, particularly in areas with higher elevations. Spring and autumn serve as brief transitional periods between the extremes of summer and winter. These seasons are characterized by milder temperatures and a relative increase in precipitation compared to summer. The Table 1 shows the average temperatures in the Guadalajara region and the mean precipitation.

Table 1: Climatic parameters from Guadalajara 1989-2010; **T:** Monthly/annual mean temperature (°C) , **TM:** Monthly/annual mean daily maximum temperatures (°C), **Tm:** monthly/annual mean daily minimum temperatures (°C), **R:** Monthly/annual mean precipitation (mm). (Agencia Estatal de Metereologia, n.d.)

Month	T	TM	Tm	R
January	4,90	10,70	-1,00	35,00
February	6,30	13,00	-0,40	32,00
March	9,50	17,00	1,90	25,00
April	11,10	18,40	3,80	50,00
May	15,50	23,50	7,50	53,00
June	20,80	29,90	11,70	25,00
July	23,70	33,50	13,70	12,00
August	22,70	31,90	13,60	13,00
September	18,70	27,40	10,00	28,00
October	13,90	20,90	6,80	68,00
November	8,30	14,70	1,90	42,00
December	5,50	11,00	-0,10	46,00
∅	13,41	20,99	5,78	35,75

2.4.3. Agricultural structure in Guadalajara

According to the *Atlas del Censo Agrario* (Instituto Nacional de Estadísticas, 2020) in 2020, the Guadalajara region was home to 4,832 agricultural holdings. Collectively, these farms encompassed a Utilized Agricultural Area (UAA) totaling 451,206.84 hectares. This area comprises arable land — which includes crop fields, fallow land, kitchen gardens, and land under woody crops — and land allocated for permanent pasture. The predominant size according to the UAA of farms in this province is bigger than 50 ha. Of the available arable land, 70.82% was actively utilized. Only 21 operations had greenhouse. Livestock farming within the province showed a total livestock count of 102,952.5 Livestock Units (LSU), distributed across 550 farms. Poultry emerged as the dominant livestock category in this region. The demographics of farm ownership in Guadalajara show that 21% of farms are operated by women. 13.34% of farm managers were under the age of 45. The percentage of farm

managers with formal agricultural training stood at 3.28%. The region's low commitment to sustainable farming practices was evidenced by the fact that 5.52% of the UAA was dedicated to organic farming. The percentage of organic poultry was negligible at 0%. While no precise information for Guadalajara is available, in Spain approximately 2.2 million hectares are managed under the principles of conservation agriculture (Asín, 2023).

In 2021, the average monthly income for Spanish farmers was 402.03€, excluding the CAP (Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación, 2021). Between 2022 and 2023, agricultural workers in the Castilla-La Mancha region experienced a salary increase of 3.1% (Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación, 2024). This rate of increase positions Castilla-La Mancha farmers within the lowest quartile of annual wage growth nationally within Spain.

In Spain, the Agricultural Value Added represented 2.61% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in 2021, displaying significant regional variation — from as little as 0.07% in the Community of Madrid to as much as 8.46% in Castilla-La Mancha (Instituto Nacional de Estadísticas, 2020). In 2022, the Gross Value added from agriculture, livestock, forestry, and fishing approximated €31.5 million, which marked an annual decrease of 5.7% (INE, 2023).

2.5. Influences

The factors influencing soil conservation include a complex web of elements. These influences are characterized by a set of economic, environmental and socio-cultural factors that encourage farmers to invest in soil conservation management.

2.5.1. Economical Influences

One of the primary influences for farmers to embrace soil conservation measures is the prospect of economic benefits. This is evidenced by studies showing that farmers, such as those in the Netherlands, are inclined to adopt conservation measures when they correlate with increased yields and cost savings (Janssen & van Ittersum, 2007). In the United States, the promise of profitability and reduced input costs has similarly encouraged the uptake of conservation tillage (Gowdy, 2008). Beyond direct economic gains, financial incentives like subsidies or tax reliefs, carbon markets, and payments for ecosystem services further incentivize sustainable practices (Liu *et al.*, 2010; Kutter *et al.*, 2011). Nonetheless, financial incentives alone may not be adequate for fostering sustained behavioral change, as evidenced by farmers reverting to conventional methods post-agri- AES funding (Mills *et al.*, 2017). The literature suggests that, while monetary incentives are crucial, they alone cannot effectuate long-lasting changes in soil management practices (Braito *et al.*, 2020).

2.5.2. Socio-Cultural Influences

The mixture of social and cultural factors provides a substantial influence on farmers' decision-making. Community norms, peer behavior, and societal values shape the adoption of conservation practices (Delaroche, 2020). Studies have found that farmers are more likely to engage in conservation tillage when they perceive their peers doing the same (Muñoz-Rojas, 2018) and are part of communities that value environmental stewardship (Shortall, 2019). The valuation of social norms and the perception of others' expectations significantly influence farmer behavior (Lapinski & Rimal, 2005), with those participating in AES placing considerable weight on their public image and peer opinions (Mills *et al.*, 2017). Enhancing their stature and public image can serve as potent motivators, potentially leading to benefits like enhanced reputation and sales opportunities (Atari *et al.*, 2009).

Culturally, the significance of soil and agriculture varies, often intertwined with local traditions and identity (Herrick *et al.*, 2012; Avelino & Wittmayer, 2016). A culture of sustainability may develop where such practices are not only acceptable but valued, influencing farmers to conserve soil as a reflection of cultural beliefs. The exchange of knowledge among farmers is another cultural aspect that fosters sustainable methods (Sligo & Massey, 2007; Oreszczyń *et al.*, 2010), with a sense of duty often guiding their conservation actions (Mills *et al.*, 2017).

2.5.3. Objective Farmer's characteristics

As Bartkowski and Bartke's review (2022) highlights, objective characteristics of farmers influence their decision-making processes. Several studies have examined the role of age in shaping farmers' choices (Knowler & Bradshaw, 2007; Defrancesco *et al.*, 2007; Atari *et al.*, 2009; Burton, 2014). However, the findings indicate no definitive correlation between age and the implementation of environmental practices. While older farmers may rely on traditional methods, younger farmers, having grown up during an era of increased awareness around climate change and sustainability, are generally more inclined to adopt environmentally friendly practices (Brodt *et al.*, 2006). In addition, the link between age and experience is important (Burton, 2014). This is relevant in the context of AES. Farmers with more experience, especially those who have participated in previous AES initiatives, are more likely to engage with and commit to future environmental programs (Defrancesco *et al.*, 2007)

Furthermore, gender differences also play a role in shaping environmental behavior in agriculture. Studies suggest that women in the agricultural sector tend to be more environmentally oriented than their male counterparts, demonstrating a stronger inclination toward adopting sustainable and conservation-focused practices (Boon *et al.*, 2010; Burton, 2014).

Education is often seen as a key factor influencing farmers' willingness to adopt sustainable practices, with higher education levels generally associated with greater openness to environmentally friendly

methods (Burton, 2014). Several studies support this link (Lambert *et al.*, 2007; Best, 2009; Barreiro-Hurlé *et al.*, 2010), suggesting that education increases awareness and understanding of sustainability. However, other studies (Defrancesco *et al.*, 2007; Finger & Lehmann, 2012) have found no clear relationship, indicating that factors may hold a stronger influence on farmers' decisions.

2.5.4. Objective Farm's characteristics

Several objective characteristics of farms can significantly impact farmers' decision-making processes, particularly regarding environmental practices.

The tenure of a farm, whether it is owned or rented, is often linked to the willingness of farmers to invest in long-term sustainable practices. However, no connection could be found for this, rather the relationship between the tenant and landlord is of importance (Leonhardt *et al.*, 2019). Farm size is another influential factor, with larger farms generally being better positioned to adopt new technologies and practices due to greater access to financial resources and economies of scale (Brown *et al.*, 2020). Conversely, small farms often face financial and operational constraints that limit their ability to engage in sustainable practice (European Commission, 2020b). However, there are exceptions where small farms, especially organic or niche farms, demonstrate strong environmental stewardship (Ricciardi *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, the biophysical characteristics of a farm, such as soil type, topography, and climate, also play a role in shaping farm sustainable soil management practices. Farms in less favorable conditions may focus more on short-term gains, as they face higher risks and uncertainties (Pastusiak *et al.*, 2019). Studies also indicate that farms with natural advantages may be more willing to allocate land for ecological preservation due to the lower opportunity costs involved (Adams *et al.*, 2010; Bryan *et al.*, 2011).

2.5.5. Environmental awareness

Environmental concerns, including awareness of climate change and soil degradation, also prompt soil conservation efforts. Farmers who exhibit empathy and care for the environment are likely to undertake conservation practices (Sheeder & Lynne, 2011; Bartkowski & Bartke, 2018) and engage in forest or wetland conservation programs (Johansson *et al.*, 2013). The perception of environmental and health risks influences the adoption of sustainable practices (Mills *et al.*, 2017), and awareness of climate risks enhances support for mitigation strategies (Arbuckle *et al.*, 2015). Yet, the delayed and uncertain nature of environmental risks can lead to a diminished perception of these risks, impacting the willingness to adopt sustainable practices (Gattig & Hendrickx, 2007). For instance, French farmers' willingness to implement conservation tillage was linked to their belief in its climate change mitigation potential (Eglin *et al.*, 2011).

3. State of the Art

In this chapter, I will explain the background and current state of research on agricultural behaviour and decision-making based on the work of Dessart *et al.* (2019). It is important to underline that decisions are often not made rationally as they are influenced by various biases. Farmers' decision-making strongly depends on their perception of the benefits and costs associated with certain agricultural practices such as no-till or crop rotation (Sattler & Nagel, 2010). Some of these practices are seen as highly beneficial and cost-saving, while others are seen as less profitable.

Dessart *et al.* (2019) identified three main behavioral factors - *dispositional, social and cognitive* - that together influence the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices. These factors and their specific sub-units are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Levels of different factors that affect the implementation of sustainable practices. Based on Dessart *et al.* (2019)

3.1. Dispositional factors

Dispositional factors refer to stable personality traits that are closely associated with emotional states (Schmidt-Atzert *et al.*, 2014). These internal characteristics include elements such as personality, motivation, values, beliefs, general preferences, and goals.

A farmer's willingness to adopt sustainable practices is significantly influenced by their *resistance to change* (Burton *et al.*, 2008). Farmers with lower openness to new experiences may be particularly reluctant to embrace change (Vanclay & Lawrence, 1994; Dessart *et al.*, 2019). Another crucial aspect is

the *status quo bias*, where existing practices are preferred because any change is perceived as a potential loss. This bias is closely tied to resistance to change (Samuelson & Zeckhauser, 1988).

Risk tolerance, a central concept in behavioral economics and also a dispositional factor, is closely linked to personality and openness to new experiences (Frey *et al.*, 2017). *Risk tolerance* can also be shaped by cultural context: People in collectivist cultures tend to be less risk-averse compared to those in individualistic societies (Weber & Hsee, 1998).

Moral concerns, *ethical principles*, and concern for the welfare of others further influence farmers' decisions. Organic farmers, for instance, are generally more concerned with doing "the right thing," than conventional farmers, indicating a strong sense of moral responsibility (Mzoughi, 2011). Studies suggest that farmers who are members of environmental organizations, which can be seen as an indicator of environmental awareness, are more willing to bear the additional costs of certain sustainable practices (Palm-Forster *et al.*, 2017). Additionally, *avoiding guilt* is another motivator for adopting organic practices (Mzoughi, 2011). Organic farmers often report greater satisfaction with their choices compared to conventional farmers (Mzoughi, 2014). Conversely, farmers who believe they are already doing enough to protect the environment may be less inclined to alter their current practices (Dessart *et al.*, 2019).

3.2. Social Factors

Interpersonal relationships influence farmers' decisions to adopt more sustainable practices (Dessart *et al.*, 2019). Social norms, in the broadest sense, are collective representations of acceptable behavior, expectations, and trust. Social learning can be a key process through which social capital is built among individuals interacting within social networks (Rust *et al.*, 2023).

Farmers' decisions to adopt sustainable practices are often shaped by the behavior of their neighbors, a phenomenon known as *descriptive norms* — essentially, what others are actually doing (Dessart *et al.*, 2019). For example, if farmers are aware that others in their region are using conservation tillage, this awareness can positively influence their own adoption of such practices (D'Emden *et al.*, 2008). There are several reasons why clusters of neighboring farmers adopting sustainable practices may form. On one hand, specific natural advantages may create favorable local conditions for adopting sustainable practices like organic farming (Lapple & Kelley, 2015). On the other hand, information exchange with neighboring farmers who have already adopted sustainable practices can be crucial for sharing insights into the actual costs, benefits, and risks involved (Thomas *et al.*, 2020). Social learning and the overall development of social capital are therefore seen as critical for the adoption of agricultural innovations within local farming systems and for participation in agri-environmental programs (Rust *et al.*, 2023). Also, when the adoption of sustainable practices by neighboring farmers reaches a significant threshold, it can signal to non-adopters that these practices have become the new norm (Dessart *et al.*, 2019). People

generally seek *social comparison*, often comparing themselves with others who are similar to them (Festinger, 1954). For example, American farmers who were part of larger networks where soil health practices were already in use were more likely to try these practices themselves (Carlisle, 2016).

Farmers participating in AES are more likely to consider the opinions of other farmers and society as important compared to those who do not participate (Defrancesco *et al.*, 2007). Dessart *et al.* describe these behavioral characteristics as *injunctive norms* — norms that dictate how people should behave. Society and the media exert normative pressure on farmers to adopt more sustainable practices (Dessart *et al.*, 2019). However, farmers may face social barriers that hinder the adoption of certain practices, leading to a "lock-in" within the community where members resist change due to negative past experiences (Marshall & Fairbridge, 1999; Rust *et al.*, 2023). For instance, conventional farmers may view practices that differ from their group's norms, such as organic farming or reduced tillage, with skepticism and criticism (Rust *et al.*, 2023).

Norms and *trust* are closely linked, as norms can serve as a foundation for building and maintaining trust (Lyon, 2000). *Trust* between individuals plays a crucial role in ensuring that information is perceived as credible and transformed into usable knowledge (Rust *et al.*, 2023). However, trust in institutions differs fundamentally from trust in other people. A lack of trust in institutions, such as governments, can significantly hinder the willingness to adopt sustainable agricultural practices (Rust *et al.*, 2023). Vice versa, high levels of trust and confidence in institutions like the government are often associated with increased acceptance of environmentally friendly practices, such as direct seeding (Turpin *et al.*, 2017). In the context of globalization and digitalization, building and maintaining trust increasingly requires the development of trust-building measures across long distances (Rust *et al.*, 2023).

For farmers, improving their public image and status can be a strong incentive to adopt more sustainable practices, such as organic farming and integrated agriculture (Michel-Guillou & Moser, 2006). Farmers who participate in AES and those practicing organic farming tend to place more importance on their public image as farmers compared to those who do not (Defrancesco *et al.*, 2007; Mzoughi, 2011). *Signaling motives* are important to them. However, a challenge with social signaling is that some sustainable agricultural practices are invisible to the general public and, therefore, receive little social recognition (Kuhfuss *et al.*, 2016). Practices like carbon sequestration in soils and the reduction of CO₂ emissions are less visible than for example reforestation (Dessart *et al.*, 2019). Additionally, citizens lacking relevant knowledge may mistakenly classify some sustainable practices as non-sustainable or fail to understand their environmental benefits (e.g., cover crops) (Dessart *et al.*, 2019). Intensive and productive agriculture is still often seen as a symbol of "good farming," and competition among farmers frequently focuses more on yield than on environmental performance (Sutherland & Darnhofer, 2012).

3.3. Cognitive Factors

The acceptance of sustainable agricultural practices is also influenced by how farmers learn, understand, and perceive these practices (Dessart *et al.*, 2019). Cognitive factors encompass farmers' knowledge and thought processes, including their views of the relative benefits, costs, and risks associated with a particular sustainable practice, as well as their self-assessment of whether they feel competent enough to successfully implement these practices.

Access to relevant and reliable information plays a crucial role in the adoption of new practices by farmers (Dessart *et al.*, 2019). Farmers transitioning to organic farming typically seek out more information and have a more positive attitude towards information gathering compared to those who do not make the switch (Läpple & Rensburg, 2011). Information about AES is also an essential prerequisite for participation in such programs (Dessart *et al.*, 2019). The more farmers feel that they can easily implement the practices associated with an AES, the more likely they are to participate (Defrancesco *et al.*, 2007). Knowledge exchange is most effective in agricultural contexts within diverse, trusted networks where innovation norms are already established, allowing even less influential actors to drive change (Rust *et al.*, 2023).

Adopting more sustainable practices compared to conventional methods involves both perceived costs and perceived benefits. For instance, conservation tillage requires the purchase of specialized planting equipment but also results in time and labor savings, as well as long-term improvements in soil fertility, which can have positive financial outcomes (Knowler & Bradshaw, 2007). In organic farming, input costs are reduced, but labor costs tend to increase (Läpple & Rensburg, 2011).

Some sustainable practices carry greater financial risks than conventional methods (Dessart *et al.*, 2019). Organic farming, for example, is subject to more significant fluctuations in supply and demand, and not using fertilizers and pesticides increases the risk of crop failures. Farmers' perceptions of the financial risks associated with sustainable agricultural practices strongly correlate with their likelihood of adopting them (Trujillo-Barrera *et al.*, 2016). Additionally, the perception of environmental and health risks can influence the adoption of sustainable practices. For instance, organic farmers are more likely to recognize the risks of poor water quality to human health than conventional farmers (Toma & Mathijs, 2007). Similarly, farmers who perceive the risks of climate change to agriculture as high are more inclined to support climate mitigation measures (Arbuckle *et al.*, 2015). Ultimately, farmers' decisions are often more influenced by potential yield losses due to an agri-environmental contract than by potential income gains from lower input costs and the higher market value of their products (Colen *et al.*, 2016).

The concept of the "tragedy of the commons" (Hardin, 1968) can help explain why farmers often place more weight on personal financial costs than on public environmental costs in their decision-making. The costs of sustainable practices are paid by individual farmers, while the benefits of these practices are distributed among other farmers and society as a whole (Piñeiro *et al.*, 2020). This dynamic may lead

farmers to prioritize personal benefits over ecological advantages when deciding whether to join an agri-environmental program.

4. The Q-Methodology

The first basic principles of the Q-Methodology lie in psychology and were introduced by William Stephenson in 1935. Q-Methodology, with its unique "qualiquantological" nature, proves to be a valuable tool for systematically studying subjective attitudes and opinions, as highlighted by Watts and Stenner (2005). As an explorative approach, the Q-Methodology assists in unravelling complex topics, providing orientation by disentangling intertwined subjective perspectives into predefined distinct points of view (Grimsrud *et al.*, 2020). Widely applied beyond its origins in psychology, Q-Methodology has found use in communication and political sciences (Barry & Proops, 1999; Byrne *et al.*, 2017), and has recently been employed in environmental conservation and sustainability research (Curry *et al.*, 2013; Byrne *et al.*, 2017; Braitto *et al.*, 2020). Demonstrating success in various empirical studies, particularly within socio-environmental research, its holistic approach allows for the reflection of participants' complete viewpoints while minimizing researcher bias (Watts & Stenner, 2012). The Q-Methodology is therefore ideal for identifying the various archetypes of Spanish farmers relevant to the research questions of this thesis. By applying the Q-Methodology, I can generate conclusive insights with a relatively small sample size, using both qualitative and quantitative data to uncover distinct groups of individuals who share similar perspectives.

The concept is straightforward, suitable participants organize statements covering a broad spectrum of opinions or perspectives (the Q-set) into a quasi-normal shape (the Q-sort), guided by their agreement or disagreement levels. This happens as part of interviews, usually conducted in-person. The results of the sorting are then digitalized for further analysis.

As Watts and Stenner (2012) outline, once Q-sorts have been digitised, the analysis involves Q-pattern by-person factor analysis using generic software packages or as used in this master's thesis, an open-source desktop application called Ken-Q/KADE (Banasick, 2019). This application uses principal component analysis (PCA) to extract non-rotated factors. When selecting the number of factors for subsequent rotation, criteria such as the Kaiser-Guttman criterion (Guttman, 1954), the total explained variance, the number of significant loadings on a factor and the interpretability of the factors are taken into account (Brown, 1993). Once the number of factors is determined, factor rotation is performed, either by a mathematical method such as Varimax or by manual rotation, with the aim of maximising the explained variance. Next, factor loadings are examined in the analysis, with the most representative Q sorts having significantly high loadings on a factor, indicating an alignment with the perspective represented in that factor (Watts and Stenner, 2012). Finally, the loaded factors guide the development of descriptive representations of typical factors based on a combination of typical Q sorts and their explanations from the associated interviews (Braitto *et al.*, 2020).

Summarizing the essence of the Q-Methodology, it involves the application of factor analysis by person, a methodological approach that allows for the establishment of correlations between the Q-sort and individual participants. This process facilitates the identification of groups of participants who exhibit similar sorting patterns in their Q-sorts, thereby indicating a shared perspective or opinion among these identified groups. (Fairweather & Klonsky, 2009; Dieteren et al., 2023)

4.1. The Q-Set

Before initiating the Q-Methodology and proceeding with the subsequent interview, it is essential to generate a set of statements that collectively address the discourse related to the subject matter of interest (Watts & Stenner, 2012). In general, a typical Q-Set ranges between 40-80 statements (Watts & Stenner, 2012).

For this master's thesis, a theoretical framework was supplied by an international team of scientists (SoilX) led by *Heidi Leonhardt* and *Michael Braito*. This framework contained a wide array of variables that impact farmers' behaviour towards their soils, based on relevant literature, project reports, and experts. To serve as an effective Q-set, it must accurately represent all potential opinions and strive for balance, thereby minimizing bias towards any specific viewpoint (Watts, 2015).

The Q-set developed included statements from the following categories: economic considerations, environmental awareness, farm and farmer's context, natural context, knowledge and experience, institutional and social environment. Subsequently, a crucial step involved in the Q-Methodology entails making sure that the Q-set, which forms the essence of the method, is not only comprehensible to farmers but also versatile and reflective of the investigated issue. This involves a multi-step process where the initial statements are deliberated upon, adapted, specified, and clarified. It is crucial for the success of the method that these statements are unique and consistently articulated (Watts & Stenner, 2012). To ensure this, each statement was shortened by creating a superordinate sentence that initiated all the following statements (Figure 3). This made the Q-set more understandable.

Figure 3: Superordinate sentence and exemplary statements.

Furthermore, any statement that was believed to be too specific underwent reformulation. For instance, the statement “*I think of the experiences that people from my immediate environment have had with their soil management.*” was revised to read as “(When I work with my soil, it is important to me) ... *to rely on the experiences of colleagues.*”

Given that the Q-Methodology does not specify a fixed number of statements for a Q-set, it is sensible to incorporate a satisfactory quantity that comprehensively captures all relevant aspects of a topic. However, it is essential to strike a balance, recognizing that an excessive number of statements may diminish participants' motivation and concentration, (Watts & Stenner, 2012). During the review process, some statements were either removed or merged due to overlap with others. Additionally, some supplementary statements were introduced to complement the Q-set.

Consistent with these considerations, the final Q-Set comprised 45 statements, as illustrated in Table 2. These statements were utilized and translated across all countries participating in SoilX. For this study, the statements were translated into Spanish (Appendix A).

Table 2: The Q-set contains 45 statements. The statements are numbered and listed according to their category. All of the statements refer to the opening sentence.

Category	No.	Statement	Source
When I work with my soil, it is important for me...			
Social environment	1	... that my plots look tidy and neat.	Ryan <i>et al.</i> , 2003; Schneider <i>et al.</i> , 2010; Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
	2	... to preserve the soil for future generations.	Ryan <i>et al.</i> , 2003; Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Economic consideration	3	... to consider the costs involved.	Carlisle, 2016; Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
	4	... to ensure the long-term economic viability of my farm.	Carlisle, 2016; Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
	5	... to prioritize short-term profit	Carlisle, 2016; Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Institutional environment	6	... to receive subsidies for what I do.	Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Economic consideration	7	... to maximize crop yields in this year.	Walder & Kantelhardt, 2018
Farm(er) Context	8	... how far a plot is away from the farmhouse.	Barbayjannis <i>et al.</i> , 2009; Lahmar, 2010; Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
	9	... to hand it over to my successors in a good condition.	Cullen <i>et al.</i> , 2020
	10	... that it is possible to work with the machines I have access to.	Bartkowski & Bartke, 2018
	11	... whether I own the plot	Foguesatto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Knowledge and experience	12	... to rely on what I learned in my training or education.	Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
	13	... to rely on the experiences of colleagues.	Bartkowski & Bartke, 2018
	14	... to rely on my own practical experiences.	Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020

Social environment	15	... to do what I believe in.	Happel <i>et al.</i> , 2022
Farm(er) context	16	... to consider how neighbouring plots are farmed.	Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Social environment	17	... to consider how it impacts my neighbours.	Ryan <i>et al.</i> , 2003; Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Economic consideration	18	... to minimize working time.	Dwyer <i>et al.</i> , 2008; Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Knowledge and experience	19	... to rely on traditional, handed-down knowledge.	Karali <i>et al.</i> , 2014; Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
	20	... to rely on the advice from advisory services.	Dessart <i>et al.</i> , 2019
Farm(er) context	21	... how long I will continue to farm.	Karali <i>et al.</i> , 2014; Carlisle, 2016; Leonhardt <i>et al.</i> , 2019; Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Institutional environment	22	... that I don't have to deal with more paperwork than necessary.	Walder & Kantelhardt, 2018
Knowledge and experience	23	... to rely on the latest recommendations from research.	Serebrennikov <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Institutional environment	24	... not to come in conflict with legal regulations.	Karali <i>et al.</i> , 2014; Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Environmental awareness	25	... to mitigate negative effects from extreme weather events.	Mitter <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
	26	... to reduce soil erosion.	Mitter <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
	27	... to prevent pests.	Mitter <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Knowledge and experience	28	... to know the plot's soil quality data.	Prokopy <i>et al.</i> , 2008
	29	... to meet the requirements of my buyers.	Happel <i>et al.</i> , 2022
Social environment	30	... to meet the expectations of society.	Karali <i>et al.</i> , 2014; Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
	31	... to produce food for society.	Karali <i>et al.</i> , 2014; Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Environmental awareness	32	... how my actions impact the environment.	Burton, 2004; Burton <i>et al.</i> , 2008; Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Natural context	33	... that I work together with nature.	Prokopy <i>et al.</i> , 2008; Delaroche, 2020
Environmental awareness	34	... how my actions impact soil organisms such as earthworms.	Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Social environment	35	... how others perceive my actions.	Walder & Kantelhardt, 2018
Farmer's context	36	... that the work gives me pleasure.	Karali <i>et al.</i> , 2014; Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020

Economic consideration	37	... to avoid economic risks.	Karali <i>et al.</i> , 2014; Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
	38	... to ensure a stable yield in the long term.	Bartkowski & Bartke, 2018
Farmer's context	39	... that I try new practices.	Knowler & Bradshaw, 2007; Prager & Posthumus, 2010; Braitto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
	40	... to increase organic matter.	Serebrennikov <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Environmental awareness	41	... to prevent nutrient losses.	Serebrennikov <i>et al.</i> , 2020
	42	... to minimize machinery use.	Bartkowski & Bartke, 2018
	43	...to protect water resources.	Delaroche, 2020
	44	...to consider climatic changes.	Bartkowski & Bartke, 2018
	45	...to increase the soil's water retention capacity.	Bartkowski & Bartke, 2018

4.2. The Questionnaire

Apart from the Q-Set, a questionnaire was formulated to gather additional information about the farmers. This questionnaire aimed to capture details such as age, education, farm characteristics, and current soil management practices (Appendix B).

To assess comprehensibility and coherence, and if necessary, to make improvements, the questionnaire and Q-Set underwent a pre-testing involving two individuals from Spain with agricultural backgrounds. Following the completion of the pre-test, both participants — one being a farmer and the other an agricultural politician — engaged in a discussion concerning the questionnaire, the Q-Set, and the Q-Methodology as a whole. Neither participant had additional opinions or statements to add.

4.3. Interview Procedure – The Q-Sort

The duration of the interviews averaged 45 minutes, with a range from 25 minutes to approximately one and a half hours. The interviews did not require any preparation from the farmers. Conducted in Spanish, each session was recorded with informed consent (Appendix C), followed by transcription and anonymization for data analysis.

The interview protocol, as delineated in Appendix F, included a structured guide with initial questions. This was succeeded by a Q-sort procedure and questions exploring the concept of the 'Good Farmer'. In a short questionnaire at the end of the interview, I gathered data on management practices, farmers' perspectives on the qualities constituting a good or poor farmer, and sociodemographic information. Interviews typically commenced with a series of open-ended questions lasting approximately 10 to 15 minutes, designed to facilitate a conversational tone and encourage the participants to speak freely. Questions addressed the farm's operational details, management, and production conditions, including specific

inquiries about soil management practices and adaptations to climate change, thereby leading into the Q-sort methodology.

The central component of the interview involved the Q-sort, where farmers organized statements relating to their soil management practices. Although the farmers were generally rather reserved, participants provided insightful information during this exercise. In the sorting, each participant sorted the Q-set of 45 statements into a forced quasi-normal shape regarding how she or he would tend to agree or disagree (see Figure 4). The statements were printed on separate cards (see Figure 3). I followed the method proposed by Watts (2015).

Figure 4: Forced choice distribution of the Q-Sort

In the first step, the farmers were asked to sort the statements in three piles; 1) *do not agree*, 2) *neutral*, and 3) *do agree*. I had them sort all these given statements according to their gut feeling, what is not important and what is important. In the second step, I presented sorting aids for the forced choice distribution for the Q-sort. The aids were numbered from -4 to +4 and showed the participants how many items could be sorted under each number in regard to their perceived importance. Overall, the pile with the statements participants agreed upon was larger, compared to the others. Therefore, I asked them to take the pile of the "don't agree"-statements first and let them decide which two statements of this pile they agree with the least. Those two items were placed at -4. I then asked them to decide what now were the four remaining statements that they disagreed with the most. Those items were put at -3, and so on until the last item of this pile was sorted. Then, they were asked to move on to the pile of the 'do agree'-statements. I let them first decide which two statements they agree with the most. These were the statements they considered most important for their soil management and were ranked at +4. Then they were asked to make a choice of which four statements of the remaining items they considered the most important for them. Then it was the pile of remaining cards — the neutral pile — that was placed in the middle first, starting with the most important statement and then the least important statement. After they

sorted all the statements, I asked them to look carefully at the final sort and to switch items if they were not.

The final stage of the -Sort included probing questions regarding decision-making processes during the Q-sorting, difficulties encountered, and an invitation for the farmers to explain, justify or add to their viewpoints. This provided an opportunity to clarify the meaning behind longer deliberations or ambiguous interpretations. Following this, the discussion about the 'Good Farmer'¹ ensued, marking the end of the structured interview process.

4.4. Ethical consent

Throughout the study, great importance was placed on maintaining the anonymity and confidentiality of the participants. Ethical considerations were closely observed at every stage of the research process, guaranteeing that the outcomes would be both valid and ethically sound. The consent form for this study is based on the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna (see Appendix C).

All farmers were informed, following the GDPR, about how their data would be stored and used before the interview, and consent for data collection was required. It was verified that all participating farmers had a clear understanding of these terms. In addition, any questions and concerns farmers had about the data collection process were addressed to ensure transparency and ease any concerns.

4.5. The P-Set

The initiation of data collection involves choosing farmers who are willing to take part in the Interviews. To ensure that the Q-Methodology delivers reliable results, the participants, known as the P-set, must have a clear and distinct position on the topic (Exel & Graaf, 2005). The P-Set must not necessarily be large but rather include a range of different viewpoints (Brown, 1993; Zabala & Pascual, 2016).

To identify farmers fitting the criteria for this study, various channels and methods were employed for outreach. Attempting to engage them through diverse communication channels, I encountered challenges, particularly with Spanish farmers who showed generally low interest in conversing. Despite initial optimism, no substantial response was generated from university contacts. The primary source of participants for this master's thesis emerged from the agricultural association APAG (Asociación

¹ The concept of the "Good Farmer" is relevant to the SoilX project but not to this study. The "Good Farmer" project explores how farmers' perceptions of what it means to be a "Good Farmer" influences their views on soil management practices.

Provincial de Agricultores y Ganaderos y SAT Coagral). APAG, beyond its role in collective purchasing and marketing, plays a crucial role in providing professional education and agricultural advice in the region of Guadalajara. Using the APAG network, farmers were identified through word of mouth, the distribution of participant information sheets, and the implementation of a snowball system. The participant information sheet can be found in Appendix D.

The participant information sheet comprehensively outlined the study's purpose, the interview process, and ethical considerations. Not every interested farmer could partake in the study, as they needed to meet the following criteria:

- I. Cultivate at least some cropland.*
- II. Be based in Guadalajara.*
- III. Serve as the main farm manager responsible for decision-making in land management practices.*

Following each interview, participants were provided with at least one participant information sheet, encouraging them to motivate friends and fellow farmers to join the study. Ultimately, a total of 23 farmers who fulfilled all the outlined criteria were identified and interviewed.

Between April and early May of 2023, I conducted a series of semi-structured interviews that included the Q-methodological sorting. This qualitative research phase involved visiting farmers directly on their farms, though the majority of interviews were held in conference rooms provided by APAG, optimizing the convenience for participants who were already present for consultations or similar activities, thus facilitating a larger sample size.

The study included a sample of 23 farmers from various regions within Guadalajara, Spain, to ensure a comprehensive representation of agricultural practices in the area. It is noteworthy that among the interviewed farmers, only two identified themselves as female, indicating a notable gender disparity among the participants. The participants were 32 to 63 years old, with an average age of 51.5. This age diversity contributes to a nuanced understanding of how different generations approach soil management practices. Educational backgrounds varied significantly among the participants, with 8 farmers having received vocational school education, 9 possessing a secondary school education, and 5 holding a university education. The sizes of the farms exhibited considerable variability, ranging from 18.5 hectares to 800 hectares, with an average farm size of 314.1 hectares. Approximately 64.5% of participants farmed area were rented.

In terms of farming practices, one participant among the 23 farmers practised organic farming. Crop rotation practices varied widely, ranging from 2 to 9 crops per field, with an average rotation of 5.5. Furthermore, two farmers operated mixed farms, incorporating both crop cultivation and livestock

management. The Livestock Units (LSU) on these mixed farms averaged 750, with 1 LSU corresponding to one dairy cow.

In summary, the detailed demographic and operational characteristics of the sampled farmers (as can be seen in *Table 3*) provide a robust foundation for analysing the multifaceted influences on attitudes and behaviours regarding soil management practices in the Guadalajara region.

4.6. Q-Analysis

Q-Methodology employs factor analysis to discern the structure within a group of variables, effectively revealing commonalities and distinct viewpoints among participants. Unlike conventional factor analysis, which focuses on items, Q-Methodology emphasizes the subjectivity of respondents by treating their responses as variables, enabling a by-person factor analysis (Brown, 1993; Watts, 2015).

For this research, the factor analysis was performed using the KADE software (Banasick, 2019), which generates outputs like to those of PQMethod, a program frequently used in contemporary Q-studies (Dieteren et al., 2023). KADE provides additional functionality such as relative statement rankings between factors and visualizations of composite factors, enriching the interpretative phase. The Q-sorts were conducted with printed statements and then photographed; I digitized the statements and coded them into a consolidated file for analysis within KADE. This analysis entailed a sequence of steps, incorporating three pivotal decisions: the selection of the number of factors, the extraction method, and the rotation approach.

The procedure commenced with the loading of data into KADE, leading to the generation of a correlation matrix that illustrates the interrelations between all Q-sort. Next, the decision on the type of factor analysis was made, with options including centroid factor analysis and PCA. Although Watts and Stenner (2012) advocate the use of centroid factor analysis, in this case I decided in favour of PCA because it offers one optimal mathematical solution and makes interpretation simpler.

Post-extraction, the software calculated *eigenvalues* and the *variance* each factor accounted for. In alignment with the Kaiser-Guttman criterion and the scree test, three factors with eigenvalues exceeding 1.00 were retained, indicating they explained more variance than a single Q-sort and were thus significant (Kaiser, 1960). Factor rotation can be performed using either varimax or judgmental rotation, both of which are orthogonal methods that maintain perpendicular axes. Varimax rotation is particularly effective because it optimizes the explanation of variance, ensuring that each Q-sort has a high loading on only one factor, thus maximizing the variance explained in the sample (Watts & Stenner, 2012). This is why I chose to apply varimax rotation in this work.

In the last phase of the analysis, KADE outlined the factors and the extent to which each participant's Q-sort correlated with them. Notably, KADE can signal Q-sorts that exemplify a specific factor. The threshold

for factor loading significance was set to $p > 0.01$. The software's outputs include factor loadings, z-scores, and statements that either unify or distinguish between viewpoints for narrative construction. Z-scores are standardized measures used to assess the level of agreement a factor has with a statement, helping to distinguish between consensus and unique viewpoints (Zabala & Pascual, 2016). These scores, along with the corresponding statement rankings, information from the post-sorting interviews and general information from the farmers helped in interpreting the narrative for each viewpoint (Watts & Stenner, 2012). To really understand each factor, I took a close look at the farmers within each group, comparing them to see what they had in common. I focused on what influences mattered most and least to them and used that to figure out how to group together farmers who share similar, archetypal views. I also looked at how these groups differ from one another and where they overlap, to build a clearer and more cohesive picture.

4.7. Time contextualization of the Interviews

The subjects of this study, farmers from Spain, have reported considerable difficulties in the period following the COVID-19 pandemic. In particular, the two-year period prior to 2023 was characterized by below-average rainfall, which in the spring of the year 2023 culminated in a severe lack of rainfall. This weather pattern posed a significant risk to the viability of agriculture. The winter prior to the study was one of the driest and warmest according to the farmers, with minimal rainfall, which contributed to an increased incidence of drought-related symptoms such as reduced seed germination and soil erosion in the drought-prone region.

The sociopolitical context during the timeframe of this study was notably tense. The farmers' perceptions of governmental and societal interactions suggest a sentiment of alienation and a lack of understanding. Most of the interviewees articulated criticisms towards the CAP, specifically expressing disapproval of the terminology '*subsidy*', and displaying a preference for the term '*compensation payment*'. It was acknowledged by a consensus among the farmers that a persistence of these climatic and economic conditions in the current year could jeopardize the long-term viability of their agricultural operations. During the four-week interview period, only minimal and brief precipitation was recorded, which was insufficient to improve the general state of agricultural distress documented in the discourse. The following graph (Figure 5) shows that the weather was extremely warm during the period I conducted the interviews in comparison to the year before.

Figure 5: Temperature in degree Celsius of Guadalajara in April of 2022 and April of 2023 reported by hour, color-coded in bands. On the Y-Axis the hours of the day are shown, while the X-Axis present the day. (Weather Spark, n.d.)

5. Results

In a Q-methodological investigation, the ultimate outcomes are narratives describing collective perspectives, as exemplified by Braitto et al., 2020. These narratives result from a synthesis of qualitative interpretations derived from the Q-analysis outcomes and post sorting interviews with participants regarding the Q-set.

The chapter is organized as follows: the initial section outlines key aspects of the statistical analysis of the Q, subsequently presenting the narratives that explain farmers' viewpoints, highlighting both commonalities and differences.

5.1. The Guadalajarean farmer

As outlined in chapter 4.6, the best result for representing the views of farmers in Guadalajara is achieved with three factors. The farmers sampled in this study show a notable degree of homogeneity, as shown in Table 3. Variations in age within the individual factors are marginal. Notably, farmers categorized under factor 2 (F2) oversee the most extensive land area, amounting to 344.3 hectares. Merely two female participants were included in the study, with one each affiliated with factor 1 (F1) and factor 3 (F3). Furthermore, most of the farmers had completed upper secondary school, whereas only 22.7% possessed a university degree.

Table 3: Respondents' characteristics for the full sample and by factor (F1-F3).

	full sample	F1	F2	F3
Number of farmers	23	10	7	5
Age (mean years)	51,5	52,6	50,6	48,4
Farm size (mean ha)	314,4	283,4	344,3	297,6
Gender (male)	21 (91,3%)	9	7	4
Level of education				
Vocational	8 (36,4%)	2	3	3
Secondary	9 (40,9%)	5	3	1
University	5 (22,7%)	3	1	1

As shown in chapter 2.4 the geographical region of Guadalajara in Spain exhibits not only variability in meteorological parameters but also diversity in soil texture, soil depth, and slope. Consequently, farmers in this region must employ distinct soil management practices tailored to their specific contextual

requirements. The questionnaire asked farmers to indicate the soil management practices that they implemented across their entire farmland, on specific portions, or not at all.

Table 4 shows that the interviewed farmers exhibit a lower propensity to adopt new methods compared to traditional farming practices. Cover crops and undersown crops are employed by only a fraction of farmers, while reduced tillage and ploughing enjoy more widespread acceptance. Interestingly, none of the farmers forego the use of chemical mineral fertilizers, although some refrain from utilizing animal manure. The practice of soil sampling is nearly ubiquitous among farmers, conducted on individual plots of land.

Table 4: Soil management practices applied by participants are categorized into archetypes resulting from Q-analysis. Specifically, F1 corresponds to the „*The soil considered*”, F2 to the “*The economic individualist*”, and F3 to “*The contemporary-minded*”.

	No	Partly	Entirely		No	Partly	Entirely
Cover Crops	19	2	0	Mineral Fertilizer	0	9	13
F1	9	1	0	F1	0	3	7
F2	5	1	0	F2	0	2	5
F3	5	0	0	F3	0	4	1
Undersown crops	19	2	0	Animal manure	11	8	3
F1	10	0	0	F1	5	4	1
F2	4	2	0	F2	3	3	1
F3	5	0	0	F3	3	1	1
Ploughing	6	10	6	Compost	20	1	1
F1	5	4	1	F1	10	0	0
F2	1	3	3	F2	5	1	1
F3	0	3	2	F3	5	0	0
Reduced tillage	6	7	3	Biochar	22	0	0
F1	2	2	0	F1	10	0	0
F2	4	2	1	F2	7	0	0
F3	0	3	2	F3	5	0	0

No till	8	10	4	Soil Testing	3	17	2
F1	2	6	2	F1	1	8	1
F2	3	3	1	F2	2	4	1
F3	3	1	1	F3	0	5	0

5.2. Statistical Analysis

Collectively, the three factors account for 51% of the variance observed in this study. The correlations between these factors are presented in Table 5, indicating the degree of similarity between viewpoints following rotation. The correlation values signify that while there exist some shared characteristics among the viewpoints, these are not overly pronounced. Nonetheless, differences emerge, as subsequently revealed in the in-depth analysis of the individual factors.

Table 5: Correlation Matrix of the three rotated factors

Factors	1	2	3
1	1	0,3806	0,5078
2		1	0,3214
3			1

Among the 23 Q-sorts analyzed, one Q-sort (F. 15) did not load significantly onto a single factor, indicating its non-representativeness for any particular factor. To enhance the distinctiveness between factors, the Q-sort of farmer 15 was not flagged, as recommended by Zabala & Pascual (2016). Factor 1 encompasses 10 Q-sorts, factor 2 comprises 7 Q-sorts, and factor 3 includes 5 Q-sorts.

Conforming to Brown's (1993) criteria, each factor should ideally consist of at least two loadings, a condition that is met in this analysis. Table 6 present the loadings of all Q-Sorts, with significant or flagged values highlighted in bold ($p > 0.01$). These loadings, analogous to z-scores, represent the correlation between an entire Q-sort and a specific factor. Consequently, factor loadings offer insights into the individual farmer's alignment with distinct viewpoints.

Table 6: This table presents the factor loadings of Q-Sorts, highlighting in bold those sorts that significantly define the factors ($p > 0.05$). The table also includes the number of defining Q-Sorts for each factor, the percentage of explained variance, and Eigenvalues.

Q-Sort	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3
19	0,74	0,36	0,11
14	0,74	0,10	-0,05
23	0,70	0,29	0,06
18	0,70	-0,07	0,37
2	0,70	0,02	0,33
3	0,58	-0,10	0,51
12	0,56	0,44	0,15
20	0,56	-0,07	0,30
8	0,45	0,32	0,26
6	0,37	0,21	-0,03
15	0,37	0,25	0,35
21	0,05	0,74	0,10
10	0,03	0,74	0,08
7	0,00	0,66	-0,04
22	0,20	0,56	-0,03
11	0,15	0,55	0,51
16	0,31	0,53	-0,07
5	0,12	0,53	0,37
13	-0,38	-0,07	0,66
4	0,45	0,08	0,64
1	0,46	0,35	0,61
17	0,21	-0,12	0,59
9	0,15	0,31	0,59
Number of defining Q-Sorts	10	7	5
Explained variance in %	21	16	14
Eigenvalue	7,24	2,5	1,8

Utilizing z-scores as indicators of the relative strength of a statement within a factor or the concordance between an archetype and a statement (Leonhardt et al., 2019), factor scores were subsequently transformed into the format of a conventional Q-sort, as outlined by Brown (1993). This conversion offers a hypothetical representation of how an archetypical farmer would have sorted the Q-statements, as seen in Figure 6,7 and 8. Furthermore, the converted z-scores facilitate a visual examination of the level of agreement or disagreement among statements within each factor and across different factors, as illustrated in Table 7.

Table 7: List of statements and factor scores. Consensus statements that do not differ significantly between any pair of factors are marked with an asterisk.

Nm	Statement	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3
When I work with my soil, it is important to me...				
1	... that my plots look tidy and neat.	2	2	-4
2	... to preserve the soil for future generations.	3	-1	1
3	... to consider the costs involved.	0	4	-2
4	... to ensure the long-term economic viability of my farm.	1	3	4
5	... to prioritize short-term profit	-2	4	1
6*	... to receive subsidies for what I do.	-2	-2	-3
7	... to maximize crop yields in this year.	-1	3	2
8	... how far a plot is away from the farmhouse.	-3	-2	-1
9	... to hand it over to my successors in a good condition.	1	-2	2
10	... that it is possible to work with the machines I have access to.	2	-2	-1
11	... whether I own the plot	-4	0	-2
12*	... to rely on what I learned in my training or education.	0	0	0
13	... to rely on the experiences of colleagues.	-3	-3	0
14*	... to rely on my own practical experiences.	1	0	0
15	... to do what I believe in.	3	0	3
16*	... to consider how neighboring plots are farmed.	-3	-4	-3
17	... to consider how my actions neighbours.	-1	-1	-3
18	... to minimize working time.	-1	2	-1
19	... to rely on traditional, handed-down knowledge.	0	0	-2
20*	... to rely on the advice from advisory services.	-1	0	0
21	... how long I will continue to farm.	-3	-4	1
22	... that I don't have to deal with more paperwork than necessary.	-1	2	-1
23	... to rely on the latest recommendations from research.	0	-1	2

24*	... not to come in conflict with legal regulations.	-2	-3	-2
25*	... to mitigate negative effects from extreme weather events.	0	-1	0
26	... to reduce soil erosion.	2	1	4
27*	... to prevent pests.	2	3	2
28*	... to know the plot's soil quality data.	0	1	1
29	... to meet the requirements of my buyers.	-2	-1	-2
30*	... to meet the expectations of society.	-1	-1	-1
31	... to produce food for society.	1	1	0
32	... how my actions impact the environment.	1	0	3
33	... that I work together with nature.	1	-1	0
34	... how my actions impact soil organisms such as earthworms.	1	0	1
35	... how others perceive my actions.	-4	-3	-4
36	... that the work gives me pleasure.	2	1	-1
37	... to avoid economic risks.	0	2	0
38*	... to ensure a stable yield in the long term.	3	3	3
39	... that I try new practices.	0	-3	-3
40	... to increase organic matter.	3	1	1
41	... to prevent nutrient losses.	4	0	3
42*	... to minimize machinery use.	0	1	0
43	...to protect water resources.	-2	2	1
44	...to consider climatic changes.	-1	-2	-1
45	...to increase the soil's water retention capacity.	4	1	2

In the following step, the statements that serve to differentiate factors (called distinguishing statements) were separated from those that show a consensus between the factors. A statement qualifies as a distinguishing statement if its z-score significantly deviates from the z-scores observed in other factors, with the threshold determined by the standard error for differences in z-scores for each pair of factors, multiplied by 1.96 to achieve a significance level of $p < 0.05$, as outlined by Zabala & Pascual (2016). Consensus statements are characterized by z-scores that do not surpass the threshold for any pair of factors, indicating similarity across factors (Zabala et al., 2018). A consensus statement thus denotes a collectively agreed-upon perspective (Brown, 1993; Zabala & Pascual, 2016; Zabala *et al.*, 2018). The identified consensus statements are denoted by asterisks in Table 7, and Table 8 presents them organized by factors.

Table 8: Consensus statements that, at a significance level of $p < 0.05$, do not exhibit significant differences between at least two factors.

Factor	No.	Statement	Factor score	Z-score
1	38	... to ensure a stable yield in the long term.	3	1,1
	12	... to rely on what I learned in my training or education.	0	-0,046
	28	... to know the plot's soil quality data.	0	0,441
	42	... to minimize machinery use.	0	0,23
	20	... to rely on the advice from advisory services.	-1	-0,422
	30	... to meet the expectations of society.	-1	-0,361
2	27	... to prevent pests.	3	1,58
	38	... to ensure a stable yield in the long term.	3	1,373
	28	... to know the plot's soil quality data.	1	0,135
	42	... to minimize machinery use.	1	0,73
	12	... to rely on what I learned in my training or education.	0	-0,038
	14	... to rely on my own practical experiences.	0	-0,06
	20	... to rely on the advice from advisory services.	0	-0,123
	25	... to mitigate negative effects from extreme weather events.	-1	-0,321
3	30	... to meet the expectations of society.	-1	-0,743
	24	... not to come in conflict with legal regulations.	-3	-1,27
	16	... to consider how neighboring plots are farmed.	-4	-1,577
	38	... to ensure a stable yield in the long term.	3	1,73
	28	... to know the plot's soil quality data.	1	0,604
	12	... to rely on what I learned in my training or education.	0	-0,142
	14	... to rely on my own practical experiences.	0	-0,14
	20	... to rely on the advice from advisory services.	0	-0,147
	25	... to mitigate negative effects from extreme weather events.	0	-0,206
	42	... to minimize machinery use.	0	0,176
	30	... to meet the expectations of society.	-1	-0,584
	6	... to receive subsidies for what I do.	-3	-1,235

When the difference between z-scores exceeds the established significance threshold, the statement is identified as a distinguishing statement. Table 9 showcases distinguishing statements for all factors. In the subsequent chapter, each factor or archetype is presented in a narrative format, with relevant rankings denoted by numbers in brackets. For instance, (26: +2) implies that the archetype would hypothetically rank statement 26 in the +2 position. Consensus statements are marked with an asterisk, for example (12: 0*), while distinguishing statements with statistical significance can be recognized by their bold typeface. The portrayal of the archetype is supplemented by participant comments, highlighted in italics.

Table 9: Distinguishing statements at $p < 0.05$ (**bold** = $p < 0.01$)

Factor	Nm	Statement	Factor Score	Z-score
1	45	...to increase the soil's water retention capacity.	4	2,15
	40	... to increase organic matter.	3	1,25
	2	... to preserve the soil for future generations.	3	1,03
	10	... that it is possible to work with the machines I have access to.	2	0,85
	26	... to reduce soil erosion.	2	0,8
	4	... to ensure the long-term economic viability of my farm.	1	0,59
	32	... how my actions impact the environment.	1	0,58
	14	... to rely on my own practical experiences.	1	0,51
	3	... to consider the costs involved.	0	0,24
	39	... that I try new practices.	0	0,1
	23	... to rely on the latest recommendations from research.	0	-0,06
	7	... to maximize crop yields in this year.	-1	-0,65
	5	... to prioritize short-term profit	-2	-0,77
	43	...to protect water resources.	-2	-1,12
	11	... whether I own the plot	-4	-1,98
35	... how others perceive my actions.	-4	-2,09	
2	5	... to prioritize short-term profit	4	2,19
	3	... to consider the costs involved.	4	2,18
	4	... to ensure the long-term economic viability of my farm.	3	1,26
	37	... to avoid economic risks.	2	1,24
	18	... to minimize working time.	2	1,01
	22	... that I don't have to deal with more bureaucracy than necessary.	2	0,93
	26	... to reduce soil erosion.	1	0,15

	15	... to do what I believe in.	0	-0,10
	41	... to prevent nutrient losses.	0	-0,11
	34	... how my actions impact soil organisms such as earthworms.	0	-0,14
	32	... how my actions impact the environment.	0	-0,20
	11	... whether I own the plot	0	-0,25
	2	... to preserve the soil for future generations.	-1	-0,25
	29	... to meet the requirements of my buyers.	-1	-0,26
	23	... to rely on the latest recommendations from research.	-1	-0,70
	9	... to hand it over to my successors in a good condition.	-2	-0,89
	10	... that it is possible to work with the machines I have access to.	-2	-1,25
	26	... to reduce soil erosion.	4	2,02
	4	... to ensure the long-term economic viability of my farm.	4	1,89
	32	... how my actions impact the environment.	3	1,43
	23	... to rely on the latest recommendations from research.	2	0,92
	21	... how long I will continue to farm.	1	0,69
	5	... to prioritize short-term profit	1	0,66
	2	... to preserve the soil for future generations.	1	0,36
	13	... to rely on the experiences of colleagues.	0	-0,34
3	31	... to produce food for society.	0	-0,38
	36	... that the work gives me pleasure.	-1	-0,55
	8	... how far a plot is away from the farm house.	-1	-0,57
	10	... that it is possible to work with the machines I have access to.	-1	-0,64
	11	... whether I own the plot	-2	-0,88
	3	... to consider the costs involved.	-2	-1,04
	19	... to rely on traditional, handed-down knowledge.	-2	-1,06
	17	... to consider how my actions impact my neighbors	-3	-1,3
	1	... that my plots look tidy and neat.	-4	-1,88

5.3. Similarities Across the Archetypes

In Chapter 5.2 and Table 8, as previously mentioned, there are similarities among the individual archetypes. These parallels are evident in the number of consensus statements in Table 8.

Archetype 1 has the fewest consensus statements, totaling only six. Archetype 3 has nine consensus statements, while Archetype 2 has the most, with eleven. A prominent shared trait among all three archetypes is the positive evaluation of creating stable yields (38: +3). The qualitative interviews revealed that yield is directly linked to profit, thus it's unsurprising that this aspect is equally important across all archetypes.

All archetypes rate their own knowledge acquired in their training or education and data collection neutrally (12: 0). For archetypes 2 and 3, relying on advisory services' advice is also deemed neutral (20: 0). However, for archetype 1, this aspect falls into negative territory (20: -1). The classification of this statement as a consensus, despite varying ratings, is explainable through the Z-score: -0.046 for archetype 1, -0.123 for archetype 2, and -0.147 for archetype 3. The Z-score allows the comparison of different data sets, even when they have different classifications, based on the fundamental principle of the Z-score in statistics.

Another consensus statement common to all three archetypes is related to meeting societal expectations (30: -1). Archetypes 1 and 3 also agree that minimized use of machinery has a marginal impact on their soil management (42: 0), while archetype 2 rates this statement as +1, explainable again by the Z-score. In addition, archetypes 2 and 3 share the view that their own practical experience has only a negligible impact (14: 0). To mitigate the negative effects of extreme weather events is another consensus statement for archetypes 2 and 3. archetype 2 scores statement 25 as -1, whereas for archetype 3, it receives a score of 0.

To summarize the findings presented, it's evident that the three distinct archetypes exhibit an emphasis on long-term planning and outcomes. Notably, the influence of external knowledge and advisory services appears to be minimal, if not entirely negligible, on the decision-making processes of these archetypes.

They do not consider external pressures to be a driving force in shaping their agricultural practices or decision-making. In conclusion, the archetypes' commitment to long-term goals, coupled with their reliance on internal expertise and their resilience to external pressures, paints a picture of self-reliant entities.

5.4. Archetypes

5.4.1. Archetype 1: The soil considered

This archetype has an Eigenvalue of 7.24, constituting the most substantial cluster among the three archetypes, encompassing 10 participants, and explaining 21% of the variance. Characterized by an average age of 52.6 years, with the age range spanning from 32 to 62 years, this archetype represents the oldest demographic and manages the smallest average land area, ranging from 18.75 ha to 516 ha. Of the

participants, 30% hold university degrees, with only one individual having an agricultural degree (farmer 14), 50% possess high school diplomas, while 20% completed middle school education. Solely one farmer within this group (farmer 14) engages in animal husbandry. Notably, the only participant adopting organic farming practices in this study, farmer (23), is affiliated with this archetype. The majority are full-time farmers, engaging in an average crop rotation of 6.2 crops.

This archetype places key priorities on enhancing soil water retention capacity (45: **+4**), preventing nutrient losses (41: **+4**), increasing organic matter (40: **+3**), and reducing soil erosion (26: **+2**). Notably, around 80% of this group embraces no-till farming, either entirely or partially. For this archetype it is important to do what he believes in (15: **+3**) while preserving the soil for future generations (2: **+3**) and maintaining the soil for successors is a consideration (9: **+1**). Central to their satisfaction is the pleasure derived from their work (36: **+2**), depending upon the availability of compatible machinery (10: **+2**), and the maintenance of overall tidiness (1: **+2**).

The economic concerns for this soil considered archetype lean towards "long-term profits" (4: **+1**) over "short-term profits" (5: **-2**), aligning with a negative aspiration to maximize crop yield in the current year (7: **-1**). Economic risks are perceived as a necessary component, viewed with indifference (37: 0), as soil conservation takes precedence over economic considerations. Scientific recommendations and new practices are of little importance for this archetype (39: **0**; 23: **0**).

Acknowledging their impact on the environment (32: **+1**), they exhibit limited concern for climate change (44: **-1**) and thus show indifference towards mitigating negative weather extremes (25: 0*). This can also be found in their view of protecting water resources (43: **-2**), which was rated lowest of all three.

Societal expectations (30: **-1***) or buyers' requirements (29: **-2**) are also notably seen as insignificant. External factors, such as potential influences on neighbors (17: **-1**), colleagues' experiences (13: **-3**), and neighboring field cultivation practices (16: **-3***), have minimal impact. This archetype prioritizes the pursuit of on his view a well-executed job (1: **+2**) aligned with own personal believes (15: **+3**), regardless of land ownership (11: **-4**). For this farmer, it doesn't matter how others perceive their actions (35: **-4**).

-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	4
** ◀ 11. ... to make a difference between the land I own and the land I do	13. ... to rely on the experiences of colleagues.	** ◀ 5. ... to prioritize short-term profit	22. ... that I don't have to deal with more bureaucracy than necessary.	28. ... to know the plot's soil quality data.	33. ... that I work together with nature.	27. ... to prevent pests.	15. ... to do what I believe in.	** ▶ 45. ...to increase the soil's water retention capacity.
* ◀ 35. ... how others perceive my actions.	21. ... how long I will continue to farm.	6. ... to receive subsidies for what I do.	18. ... to minimize working time.	** 3. ... to consider the costs involved.	** ◀ 4. ... to ensure the long-term economic viability of my farm.	36. ... that the work gives me pleasure.	** ▶ 40. ... to increase organic matter.	41. ... to prevent nutrient losses.
	8. ... how far a plot is away from the farm house.	24. ... not to come in conflict with legal regulations.	44. ...to consider climatic changes.	42. ... to minimize machinery use.	** 32. ... how my actions impact the environment.	** ▶ 10. ... that it is possible to work with the machines I have access to.	38. ... to ensure a stable yield in the long term.	
	16. ... to consider how neighboring plots are farmed.	** ◀ 43. ...to protect water resources.	30. ... to meet the expectations of society.	19. ... to rely on traditional, handed-down knowledge.	31. ... to produce food for society.	** 26. ... to reduce soil erosion.	* ▶ 2. ... to preserve the soil for future generations.	
		29. ... to meet the requirements of my buyers.	20. ... to rely on the advice from advisory services.	** ▶ 39. ... that I try new practices.	9. ... to hand it over to my successors in a good condition.	1. ... that my plots look tidy and neat.		
			** ◀ 7. ... to maximize crop yields in this year.	25. ... to mitigate negative effects from extreme weather	* ▶ 14. ... to rely on my own practical experiences.			
			17. ... to consider how my actions impact my /neighbourhood.	37. ... to avoid economic risks.	34. ... how my actions impact soil organisms such as earthworms.			
				12. ... to rely on what I learned in my training or education.				
				** 23. ... to rely on the latest recommendations from research.				

Legend

* Distinguishing statement at P< 0.05
 ** Distinguishing statement at P< 0.01
 ▶ z-Score for the statement is higher than in all other factors
 ◀ z-Score for the statement is lower than in all other factors

Figure 6: Composite Q-Sort for Factor 1 “The soil considered”

Farmer 14 encapsulates this perspective by emphasizing the commitment to work in both crop and livestock farming. The farmer underscores the significance of well-maintained soil, which, while imperceptible to society, is integral to the agricultural process.

"Because I'm a cropland farmer and livestock farmer by trade, I love a job well done. Then there are outcomes, because there are so many factors that we can't control, but I want my work to be well done. [...] After all, a well-cared for animal or a well-cared of piece of land will always yield more than a piece of field or an animal that is not well cared for. Let me see how I explain it to you. [...]"

try to have the soil in the best conditions to get the best yield possible, being within the area where we are, so the land is the main factor, without land we don't work. What we need to do, take care of it, that's what society doesn't see “.

5.4.2. Archetype 2: The economic individualist

This archetype accounts for 16% of the observed variance and is characterized by an Eigenvalue of 2.5. It encompasses seven farmers, notably the only archetype where none of the female participants is part of. The age range spans from 35 to 62 years, with an average age of 50.6. This archetype manages the largest agricultural area, averaging 344.5 hectares, with individual farms ranging from 82 to 800 hectares.

Solely one individual in this group holds a university degree, while 43% have a high school degree, and another 43% possess a low level of education. All farmers affiliated with this archetype exclusively engage in full-time field farming, abstaining from animal husbandry, and maintain an average crop rotation of 5.7.

This archetype expresses a sense of being misunderstood by both society and politics. While profitability is a common concern among Spanish archetypes, the economic individualist places particular emphasis on profits, especially short-term gains (5: **+4**). Priorities include maximizing harvest yields for the current year (7: **+3**), vigilant cost awareness (3: **+4**), and a desire to minimize economic risks (37: **+2**) while ensuring the long-term economic sustainability of the farm (4: **+3**).

In comparison to the archetype 1, the soil considered Farmer, this archetype finds the bureaucratic process (22: **+2**) associated with receiving subsidies (6: **-2***) more than just a necessary inconvenience. Farmer 16 and Farmer 22 express frustration with the increasing bureaucratic demands, describing them as burdensome and demoralizing.

This is how farmer 16 explains it:

“We go crazy with paperwork [...], they sanction you as if we were criminals. That's what I'm totally against that, they're putting beating sticks everywhere. We are talking about food. We are talking about feeding humanity and then they are, on the other hand, they are beating us to punish us.”

Farmer 22 describes it as follows:

“The bureaucracy is horrible and every year we are getting more and more behind, that is to say that the CAP and it's going to get more and more complicated, in fact, I don't know what the rest of the people have told you, but now we are very demoralized because of democracy, because of what they are demanding of us [...]. “

Despite these archetype’s efforts to address issues such as soil erosion, pest infestation (26: +1; 27: +3), and nutrient loss (41: 0), its actions are primarily driven by economic considerations rather than ecological or social concerns. The impact of soil management on the environment is considered irrelevant (32: 0), as is their effect on soil organisms (34: 0).

-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	4
16. ... to consider how neighboring plots are farmed.	24. ... not to come in conflict with legal regulations.	6. ... to receive subsidies for what I do.	* ◀ 2. ... to preserve the soil for future generations.	12. ... to rely on what I learned in my training or education.	36. ... that the work gives me pleasure.	** ▶ 37. ... to avoid economic risks.	27. ... to prevent pests.	** ▶ 5. ... to prioritize short-term profit
21. ... how long I will continue to farm.	13. ... to rely on the experiences of colleagues.	** ◀ 9. ... to hand it over to my successors in a good condition.	33. ... that I work together with nature.	14. ... to rely on my own practical experiences.	45. ...to increase the soil's water retention capacity.	** ▶ 18. ... to minimize working time.	38. ... to ensure a stable yield in the long term.	** ▶ 3. ... to consider the costs involved.
	35. ... how others perceive my actions.	44. ...to consider climatic changes.	* ▶ 29. ... to meet the requirements of my buyers.	19. ... to rely on traditional, handed-down knowledge.	42. ... to minimize machinery use.	1. ... that my plots look tidy and neat.	7. ... to maximize crop yields in this year.	
	39. ... that I try new practices.	* ◀ 10. ... that it is possible to work with the machines I have access to.	25. ... to mitigate negative effects from extreme weather	** ◀ 15. ... to do what I believe in.	31. ... to produce food for society.	43. ...to protect water resources.	* 4. ... to ensure the long-term economic viability of my farm.	
	8. ... how far a plot is away from the farm house.	17. ... to consider how my actions impact my /neighbourhood.	** ◀ 23. ... to rely on the latest recommendations from research.	20. ... to rely on the advice from advisory services.	28. ... to know the plot's soil quality data.	** ▶ 22. ... that I don't have to deal with more bureaucracy than necessary.		
		30. ... to meet the expectations of society.	* ◀ 34. ... how my actions impact soil organisms such as earthworms.	40. ... to increase organic matter.				
			** ◀ 32. ... how my actions impact the environment.					
			* ▶ 11. ... to make a difference between the land I own and the land I do					

Legend

- * Distinguishing statement at P< 0.05
- ** Distinguishing statement at P< 0.01
- ▶ z-Score for the statement is higher than in all other factors
- ◀ z-Score for the statement is lower than in all other factors

Figure 7: Composite Q-Sort for Factor 2 “*The economic individualist*”

While a sense of duty is perceived in their role as food producers for society (31: +1), decision-making is minimally influenced by the experiences of colleagues (19: 0), personal experiences (14: 0*), and advisory services (20: 0*). Although, to meet their buyers’ requirements (29: -1) has less of a value for them. This archetype ranks their own personal beliefs the lowest from all archetypes (15: 0), still taking precedence over following the latest scientific findings (23: -1) or societal expectations (30: -1*).

The condition of the soil for direct successors (9: -2) and future generations (2: -1) has limited influence on their work, and climate change is not considered crucial (44: -2). For many farmers of this archetype, the issue of climate change is politically charged. Farmer 16 expresses this sentiment as follows:

“I think it is a climate change, that I do believe, but as there has been a history of the earth, [...] but they want us to see that it is caused by man, climate change, but that is false. Because they're taking money and they're taking a lot of money out from that deception.”

This archetype dismisses working together with nature (33: -1) and external perceptions of their behavior (35: -3). New agricultural practices have minimal impact on this farmer archetype (39: -3). Farmers of this archetype are least influenced by how their neighbors cultivate their fields (16: -4) or how long they themselves will continue to operate their own farm (21: -4).

5.4.3. Archetype 3: The contemporary-minded

The final cluster comprises five farmers, explaining a variance of 14% with an associated Eigenvalue of 1.8. This archetype is distinguished as the youngest, having an average age of 48.4 years, with individuals ranging from 44 to 57 years old. On average, they cultivate 297.6 hectares of land, spanning from 188.05 hectares to 500 hectares.

Four of the five persons of this group identify as male. Regarding educational background, one possesses a university degree, one a high school diploma, and three have completed basic education. Organic farming practices are absent within this group, and all members are engaged in full-time farming, with only one participant operating a mixed farm. The average crop rotation for this archetype is 4.6.

Looking at the economic aspects of this archetype, long-term viability is a dominant concern, with a particular emphasis on ensuring enduring economic sustainability (4: +4) and maintaining a stable long-term yield (38: +3*). Contrary to other archetypes, costs (3: -2) and the avoidance of economic risks (37: 0) have a relatively lower priority. Subsidy incentives (6: -3*) have a negligible influence on this farmer's decision-making. Short-term objectives such as maximizing crop yields (7: +2) and prioritizing immediate profits (5: +1) hold some significance for this archetype.

This archetype demonstrates a positive awareness of their actions and their environmental impact (32: +3). This is one of the things that makes this archetype stand out, because compared to archetype 1, which only looks at soil health, the contemporary minded archetype seems to have a more holistic view of soils and the environment. Their decision-making aligns with personal beliefs (15: +3), encompassing initiatives to prevent soil erosion and nutrient loss (26: +4; 41: +3). This archetype prioritizes the protection of water resources (43: +1) and aims to enhance soil water-holding capacity (45: +2). They do this in alignment with their efforts to increase the organic matter (40: +1). Farmer 1 expresses this viewpoint as follows:

"There is no fertile soil. Soil is fertile because it has organic matter. Fertility is totally linked to the organic matter in the soil. And the whole issue of nutrients, of preventing pests, of... We were talking about water here, but soil with organic matter is much more resistant to drought, for example. So increasing organic matter and reducing erosion is the most important thing. It's the basics."

-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	4
35. ... how others perceive my actions.	6. ... to receive subsidies for what I do.	24. ... not to come in conflict with legal regulations.	18. ... to minimize working time.	33. ... that I work together with nature.	** ► 21. ... how long I will continue to farm.	27. ... to prevent pests.	38. ... to ensure a stable yield in the long term.	** ► 26. ... to reduce soil erosion.
** ◀ 1. ... that my plots look tidy and neat.	* ◀ 17. ... to consider how my actions impact my /neighbourhood.	* 11. ... to make a difference between the land I own and the land I do	** ◀ 36. ... that the work gives me pleasure.	42. ... to minimize machinery use.	** 5. ... to prioritize short-term profit	** ► 23. ... to rely on the latest recommendations from research.	41. ... to prevent nutrient losses.	* ► 4. ... to ensure the long-term economic viability of my farm.
	16. ... to consider how neighboring plots are farmed.	29. ... to meet the requirements of my buyers.	44. ... to consider climatic changes.	14. ... to rely on my own practical experiences.	28. ... to know the plot's soil quality data.	7. ... to maximize crop yields in this year.	** ► 32. ... how my actions impact the environment.	
	39. ... that I try new practices.	** ◀ 3. ... to consider the costs involved.	* ► 8. ... how far a plot is away from the farm house.	12. ... to rely on what I learned in my training or education.	43. ... to protect water resources.	45. ... to increase the soil's water retention capacity.	15. ... to do what I believe in.	
		** ◀ 19. ... to rely on traditional, handed-down knowledge.	30. ... to meet the expectations of society.	20. ... to rely on the advice from advisory services.	34. ... how my actions impact soil organisms such as earthworms.	9. ... to hand it over to my successors in a good condition.		
			22. ... that I don't have to deal with more bureaucracy than necessary.	25. ... to mitigate negative effects from extreme weather	40. ... to increase organic matter.			
			* 10. ... that it is possible to work with the machines I have access to.	37. ... to avoid economic risks.	* 2. ... to preserve the soil for future generations.			
				** ► 13. ... to rely on the experiences of colleagues.				
				* ◀ 31. ... to produce food for society.				

Legend
* Distinguishing statement at P< 0.05
** Distinguishing statement at P< 0.01
► z-Score for the statement is higher than in all other factors
◀ z-Score for the statement is lower than in all other factors

Figure 8: Composite Q-Sort for Factor 3 "The contemporary-minded"

This archetype acknowledges the role as a food producer for society (31: 0) less than others. Personal pleasure derived from work is of secondary importance (36: -1). Preservation of the soil for future generations (2: +1), particularly direct successors (9: +2), appears to be important for them. The ownership

status of land, whether owned or rented, has minimal impact on decision-making (11: **-2**). Farmer 4 explains it like this:

"But I believe that the main thing is to maintain the soil and that in the future it will be possible to continue cultivating on these soils. So, that's why I have given more value to that."

In contrast to relying on personal (14: 0*) and peer experiences (13: **0**), this archetype places greater reliance on the latest scientific recommendations (23: **+2**), rather than relying in traditional knowledge (19: **-2**). His reliance on the latest scientific findings is another distinctive characteristic and unique aspect of this archetype.

Consideration for the impact of actions on neighbors (17: **-3**) and the cultivation practices of neighboring fields (16: **-3***) holds little influence in their decision-making. The general perception of his actions by others is of minimal concern to him (35: **-4**). Additionally, the maintenance of orderly plots holds a minor significance for this archetype (1: **-4**).

This archetype is centered on soil protection and the environment. They are characterized by their openness to recommendations for passing on healthy soils to their successors. Farmer 9 summarizes this perspective as follows:

Farmer 9:

"If you don't like the work, it's very bad for you. You work, of course, to earn a living. You try to work well while respecting the environment in which [...] you work. Which is the soil, nature, the earth."

6. Discussion

In this final chapter, I will contextualise my findings with existing literature. Furthermore, I will answer the research questions (“Which archetypal viewpoints on soil management can be identified and what key factors influence farmers in Guadalajara, Spain, when choosing their soil management methods?”, “What challenges prevent farmers from adopting practices that favor soil health?”, “What conclusions can be drawn regarding current policy measures and how can they be improved to better support sustainable practices?”) stated in the introduction and use these results to point out policy flaws and opportunities. In the first sub-chapter, I will elaborate on the similarities of the archetypal farmers (*soil considered (F1), economical individualist (F2), contemporary minded (F3)*) formed in chapter 5. In the second sub-chapter (6.2), I will discuss the considerations of the individual archetypes and support these with interpretations and literature. In subchapter 6.3, I will use these findings to draw policy conclusions. As for chapter 6.4, I will discuss the limitations of this work.

6.1. What unites the farmers of Guadalajara

The highest ranked consensus statement across all three archetypes was to ensure a stable yield in the long term (38: +3*). A stable yield goes hand in hand with a stable economic return and therefore, according to the current literature, is of great importance to farmers (Karali *et al.*, 2014; Bartkowski & Bartke, 2018; Dessart *et al.*, 2019; Braitto *et al.*, 2020). Considering all the economic aspects addressed in the Q, all three archetypes generally ranked them high (F1-38: +3*; F1-4: +1; F2-5: +4; F2-3: +4; F2-38: +3*; F2-7: +3; F2-4: +3; F2-37: +2; F3-4: +4; F3-38: +3*; F3-7: +2; F3-5: +1). This is expected, given that farmers operate as entrepreneurs (Bartkowski & Bartke, 2018). Economic conditions are an essential factor in the decision-making behaviour of farmers. Or as farmer 7 puts it “(I)n agriculture, but in any business in the end I think, the priority for any business is to be viable.”

Interestingly, and in contrast to Carlisle (2016) findings, own knowledge acquired through training or education seems to have a neutral effect on the archetypal farmers of Guadalajara (12:0*). The same applies to their own gained practical experience (14: 0*). This suggests that, for these farmers, economic considerations might hold greater importance, potentially outweighing the value of education or peer influence (F1-16: -3*; F2-16: -4*; F3-16: -3*) in their decision-making processes. Based on this, it is important to design education and training programs that are directly linked to their economic objectives. Programs that demonstrate clear, practical benefits – such as cost savings, yield improvements or access to new markets – are likely to be better received by farmers (Bingen *et al.*, 2003). These programs should focus on practical, applicable knowledge rather than theoretical concepts to make them more relevant and effective.

As indicated in Chapter 4.7, there appears to be a general conflict between farmers and society. Farmers often feel misunderstood by society or even portrayed as the ones to blame for the climate crisis (Mills *et al.*, 2017). This suggests why it is not important for farmers in Guadalajara to meet society's expectations (30: -1*). These findings are in line with those of Braitto *et al.* (2020), who found similar results among Austrian farmers. Farmers often feel that they have an unfairly negative reputation, which can further widen the gap between them and society. Dessart *et al.* (2019) describe that citizens who lack knowledge about agricultural practices often misjudge actions and thus draw uninformed and incorrect conclusions about agricultural practices. Improving the social reputation of farmers and facilitating communication between both sides could help bridge this gap and reconnect with socially distanced farmers (Braitto *et al.*, 2020). This could also contribute to the achievement of sustainability goals, as it has been shown that farmers adopt environmentally friendly land use practices because they are committed to sustainability and want to maintain their positive social image (Mills *et al.*, 2017).

To conclude, addressing these issues requires a multifaceted approach that integrates economic incentives, targeted education, improved communication and societal engagement. By addressing both the economic concerns and social perceptions of farmers, it is possible to create a more supportive environment that encourages sustainable farming practices while maintaining the economic viability that farmers prioritize.

6.2. Archetypal Farmers and the factors shaping their decisions

It has been consistently demonstrated that farmers are a highly heterogeneous group within our society (Darnhofer *et al.*, 2005; Karali *et al.*, 2014; Carlisle, 2016; Walder & Kantelhardt, 2018; Dessart *et al.*, 2019; Braitto *et al.*, 2020; Bartkowski *et al.*, 2022). The decision to adopt or reject an agricultural measure is influenced not only by objective factors (*homo agricola economicus*), but also by a wide range of subjective values that shape the decision-making process (Bartkowski & Bartke, 2018; Dessart *et al.*, 2019). When examining the three archetypes identified in this study, we find significant overlap with the existing literature, but also some distinct features.

As described in the previous chapter, economic influences have a big impact on farmers in Guadalajara. This finding is not new in literature (Janssen & van Ittersum, 2007; Mills *et al.*, 2017; Braitto *et al.*, 2020; Bartkowski *et al.*, 2022). However, in contrast to the study by Braitto *et al.* (2020), all of the archetypes identified among Guadalajara's farmers consider the economic factors to be of importance. In their work, Braitto *et al.* identified four different archetypes, two of which fall into the ecocentric category (emphasizing a close relationship with nature) and two into the anthropocentric category (prioritizing goals such as

economic efficiency). Based on Braitto's definitions, all three of the archetypal farmers in Guadalajara can be considered anthropocentric.

Leading in this regard is the **Economic Individualist** who places the highest value on cost considerations and short-term profit (F2-3: +4; F2-5: +4). Similarly to Braitto's et al. (2020) "*Profit Maximizers*" farmers or Bartowski's et al. (2022) "*Productivist*" and "*Traditionalist*", those who share this view are concerned with efficiency and increasing economic profitability. Ecological goals are not important to them (F2-34: 0; F2-32: 0; F2-41: 0), they rate them lower than all other archetypes. This focus on efficiency means they may adopt practices that enhance productivity in the short term, even if these practices are not environmentally sustainable. They might see ecological goals as secondary or even as potential obstacles to achieving maximum efficiency (Lankoski & Thiem, 2020). When economic survival is at stake, environmental goals may seem like a lower priority, especially if they perceive that ecological practices could increase costs or reduce short-term profits (Läpple & Rensburg, 2011). What also distinguishes these archetypes is their aversion to bureaucratic paperwork (F2-22: +2), which they express in the post-sorting interviews as overwhelming and burdensome. So, it makes sense that receiving subsidies (F2-6: -2) has little effect on them.

Despite their dislike for subsidies and bureaucracy, these farmers recognize a paradox, they cannot completely do without subsidies because of the economic pressures they face. Farmer 16 explains this as follows: "*We would like to have no subsidy at all. In a survey of all farmers, I'm sure they don't want any, but fair prices that we can live with dignity. But we can't do without them, otherwise we wouldn't survive.*". This indicates a tension between their ideal of self-sufficiency and the reality of the agricultural market, where subsidies play a crucial role in ensuring their financial viability (Brown et al., 2021).

An eponymous factor for this archetypal farmer is their individualistic approach. If we look at the factors that influence this archetype the least, we see that he is not influenced by the practices of his neighbours (F2-16: -4), relying on the experiences of his colleagues (F2-13: -3) and how others perceive his actions (F2-35: -3). This archetype tends to make decisions based on personal judgment (F2-15: 0) rather than "following the crowd" or relying on the input of others. This behaviour could be based on the belief that their farm is unique and that what works for others may not work for them. They may also have had experiences in the past where following the advice of others has led to sub-optimal results, which encourages them to rely on their own judgement.

Another important aspect that contributes here emerged from the post-sorting interview, this archetypal farmer has a rather complicated relationship with society and especially with politics. Interestingly, and perhaps explaining why the farmers who share this view focus primarily on short-term success, is that to some extent they see no need for long-term investment in the soil. They rank protecting the soil for future generations (F2-2: -1) and leaving the soil in good conditions to their successors (F2-9: -2) very low. How long they continue to farm influences them the least (F2-21: -4). The low prioritization of leaving the soil in

good condition for future generations suggests a potential disconnect between current and future generations. This could be related to changing family dynamics, where younger generations are less involved in or interested in continuing the family farm due to working conditions and insufficient income (Borda *et al.*, 2023). If farmers do not see a clear line of succession or if the farming tradition is not being actively passed down, they might feel less responsible for the long-term condition of the land (Daniele, 2024). This lack of a perceived future for the farm can diminish the motivation to invest in practices that would benefit future generations.

In contrast to this is the **Contemporary Minded** archetype who is generally concerned with preserving the soil for future generations (F3-2: +1) and especially for their own successor (F3-9: +2) (Farmer 1: “*That’s also difficult because I think, you have to hand over the soil better than you took them.*”). If we draw the same comparison as with the individualistic farmer, we see that this archetype considers long-term economic goals (F3-4: +4) and a stable yield in the long term (F3-38: +3*) to be more important than short-term profits (F3-5: +1). To achieve its goals, this archetype understands the importance of integrating ecological practices into their farming approach. Acknowledging that agriculture is not just about economic gains (Dessart *et al.*, 2019) but about ensuring the long-term health of the land, this farmer carefully prioritizes a range of environmental considerations in their decision-making process. At the top of their priorities is the reduction of soil erosion (F3-26: +4). By focusing on minimizing erosion, the farmer ensures that the soil remains fertile and productive, safeguarding the land from degradation that could jeopardize future crop yields and the overall farm ecosystem (Cárceles Rodríguez *et al.*, 2022). Almost equally important to this farmer is the impact of their actions on the environment (F3-32: +3). They are aware that farming does not occur in isolation but within a broader ecological context. This awareness drives them to consider how their actions affect the surrounding environment, including the water resources (F3-43: +1; F3-45: +2). Also, by preventing the loss of nutrients (F3-41: +3) from the soil, they maintain its fertility and reduce the need for chemical fertilizers.

These archetypal farmers appear to make opportunistic decisions, as described by Karali *et al.*, (2014), particularly when they anticipate higher profits from adopting sustainable practices. The Contemporary minded archetypal farmer can best be compared with Braito *et al.* (2020) “*Pleasure Seeker*”. Comparing this archetype with the findings of Bartowski *et al.* (2022) it is possible to recognize an overlap between “*The Innovator*”, “*The Environmentalist*” and also “*The Productivist*”. This is because as we can see, the archetype I have defined has a combination of environmental and self-centered attributes. Added to this are the economic traits that all share. Among all archetypes, for this archetype, traditional knowledge (F3-19: -2) was rated lowest, while to rely on the latest recommendations from research (F3-23: +2) was rated highest. This shift from traditional knowledge to modern research can be seen as part of a broader trend towards the professionalization and modernization of farming, where traditional methods are often viewed as outdated or less effective in the context of current agricultural challenges (Thomas *et al.*, 2020).

The **Soil Considered** archetype shares many ecological aspects with the *Contemporary minded*. When making decisions, however, soil health considerations have a high importance to this archetype (F1-45: +4; F1-40: +3; F1-26: +2 F1-32: +1). This might indicate why the only organic farmer in the group shares this view. They are a mixture of the *Nature Participants* and *Traditional Food Providers* described by Braitto et al. (2020). As well as a mixture of “*The Environmentalist*” and “*The Traditionalist*” (Bartkowski et al., 2022). They are keen to improve their soil management, nonetheless they value the consideration of cost higher (F1-3: 0) than considering the climatic changes (F1-44: -1). This may be explained by the fact that this archetypal farmer prioritizes long-term investments over immediate gains, as short-term profits (F1-5: -2) or maximizing this year’s yield (F1-7: -1) are less important to him than ensuring a stable yield over time (F1-38: +3). Unlike the *Contemporary Minded* archetype, he places greater value on preserving the land for future generations (F1-2: +3) rather than focusing solely on his immediate successors (F1-9: +1). This can be interpreted as a commitment to communitarian values, where the well-being of future generations and the community as a whole is considered more important than individual or family advancement.

In summary, the viewpoints that guide farmers' decisions are intertwined and reflect a mixture of personal, socio-cultural, economic, institutional and environmental factors (Dessart et al., 2019). The differences in these viewpoints are deeply rooted in each individual's unique circumstances. A recurring theme in the interviews is the economic situation and the perception of being misunderstood. As in other studies, this study was able to establish a dichotomy between economic and ecological differences that at first glance appear to be mutually exclusive (Karali et al., 2014; Walder & Kantelhardt, 2018; Braitto et al., 2020). However, as the relevant literature also shows, many of the values and factors that lead to a decision are shared by the different viewpoints.

6.3. Policy Conclusions

In this subchapter, I will explore the challenges that farmers face when choosing or applying their soil management, drawing from insights gained through post-interviews. This part was not statistically analyzed but instead evaluated qualitatively to provide a more descriptive understanding. This discussion offers a deeper understanding of both the obstacles and opportunities within the farming community.

Throughout the interviews, many farmers expressed considerable frustration with their current situation, revealing a deep sense of neglect by politicians and a feeling of being misunderstood by society in general. This may lead to them becoming increasingly isolated.

A paradox emerges, as highlighted in the previous chapter: while many farmers are reluctant to accept subsidies, seeing them as politically charged and burdened with negative connotations, they also recognize that without such financial support their survival is insecure. This tension reflects a wider issue, where the term 'subsidy' is often met with resistance. Many of the farmers I interviewed would prefer the

term 'compensatory payments', while simultaneously receiving a fair price for their products, which they see as a more just and respectful form of support. The current state of the CAP does not adequately address the diverse needs of European farmers, as it tends to favor a one-size-fits-all approach. This approach fails to capture the complexity and heterogeneity of farming practices across Europe. As discussed in chapter 2.3.2, most subsidies are calculated on the basis of the area of land farmed, rather than taking into account the social, environmental and economic contributions that different types of farming can make (Brown *et al.*, 2021). There are several ways in which farmers could be supported more effectively. For example, AES have a significant impact on economic factors. Expanding these schemes, as well as improving information distribution, promoting stakeholder dialogues and organizing roundtable discussions, could help farmers feel more recognized and valued. As Dessart *et al.* (2019) note, knowledge is the foundation for participation in AES. The simpler and more understandable a measure appears to a farmer, the more likely he is to adopt it (Defrancesco *et al.*, 2007).

Furthermore, social networks have a crucial role to play in encouraging the adoption of environmentally friendly practices (Braito *et al.*, 2020; Targetti *et al.*, 2021). Social interactions between farmers can foster a sense of community and facilitate the exchange of valuable information and experiences (Dessart *et al.*, 2019). Strengthening these networks could help bridge the perceived gap between farmers and society. Although, this remains a challenging task, particularly in regions where relations have become tense, such as with farmers in Guadalajara. Despite these challenges, efforts must be made to promote understanding and reconciliation. Braito *et al.* (2020) suggest measures that could be effective, including public awareness campaigns led by governments, NGOs or farmers' associations; exchange visits to farms and schools; and the provision of understandable information to the general public about agricultural practices. If society begins to see farmers not as blameworthy for the climate crisis, but as essential contributors to a sustainable future, farmers will be more likely to engage in AES or similar programs (Kuhfuss *et al.*, 2016).

In conclusion, motivating farmers to adopt, maintain, and advocate for soil protection and other sustainable practices requires a multifaceted approach.

6.4. Study Limitations

The Q-Methodology proved to be a valuable tool for addressing the research questions in this study. However, as with any research approach, there are potential limitations that warrant further investigation. One limitation relates to the Q-set. Although efforts were made to include a comprehensive range of statements relevant to farmers' decision-making processes, it is challenging to ensure that the Q-set is completely exhaustive. As a result, there is a possibility that the results of the study may be influenced by this limitation. In addition, the interpretation of certain statements may vary among participants. While the post interview shed light on some of the farmers' individual interpretations, it was not possible to explore

the nuances of each statement within the scope of this thesis due to the time-intensive nature of the Q-Methodology.

Another limitation of the Q-Methodology is that it does not allow generalisations to be made about the wider population of farmers. Although the types of farmers identified in this study provide insight into different viewpoints and considerations regarding soil management practices, the study does not provide guidance on how to identify these types of farmers in practice.

The distribution of farmers' associations with specific viewpoints could be partly explained by the context in which the interviews were conducted. At the time, many farmers were dealing with the effects of the drought and related concerns, which may have influenced their responses. Due to existential fears resulting from the climatic and political situation (Chapter 4.7), it is possible that many farmers were primarily concerned about their short-term viability. In addition, the method used to recruit participants may have introduced a degree of homogeneity among respondents.

In general, most of the farmers interviewed were not particularly talkative. My status as an outsider (from another country) conducting the interviews may have led to some scepticism among participants, and language barriers, including dialect differences, required clarification during interviews, potentially disrupting the flow of dialogue. To make the process easier for the farmers, I scheduled the interviews around their existing appointments with APAG. However, this decision to conduct interviews outside the farmers' usual environment may also have influenced their responses as they were not in their familiar and safe environment.

7. Conclusions

Soil health is fundamental to agricultural productivity and sustainability, directly influencing global food security and the resilience of ecosystems (Rust *et al.*, 2023). In regions like Guadalajara, Spain, where agricultural practices must adapt to changing environmental conditions, understanding the motivations behind soil management decisions is crucial. This study contributes to this understanding by employing Q-Methodology to categorize and analyze the different perspectives of farmers regarding soil conservation. Through this approach, key factors were identified that drive or hinder the adoption of sustainable practices, providing insights that are essential for designing more effective agricultural policies.

Which archetypal viewpoints on soil management can be identified, and what key factors influence farmers in Guadalajara, Spain, when choosing their soil management methods?

This study uncovered three distinct archetypes among the farmers in Guadalajara: the *Soil Considered*, the *Economic Individualist*, and the *Contemporary Minded*. Each of these archetypes represents a different approach to soil management, shaped by a different set of priorities and influences.

- **The Soil Considered:** This archetype is characterized by a deep commitment to preserving soil health for future generations. Farmers that share this viewpoint are primarily motivated by soil health considerations, such as enhancing soil organic matter, reducing erosion, and increasing water retention. They view the soil as a living system that needs to be nurtured and protected. The long-term viability of their land is a central concern, and they are more likely to adopt practices that improve soil structure and fertility, even if these practices do not offer immediate economic benefits.
- **The Economic Individualist:** This archetype prioritizes short-term economic gains and operational efficiency. Their decision-making is heavily influenced by the need to maintain profitability in a challenging economic environment. They are more inclined to adopt practices that reduce costs or increase yields in the immediate term, often viewing environmental goals as secondary (if ever). They also tend to be skeptical of external advice and prefer to rely on their own experience.
- **The Contemporary Minded:** This archetype represents a balanced approach, where farmers aim to integrate economic viability with ecological responsibility. They understand the importance of soil conservation but are also mindful of the economic realities of farming. Their approach reflects a mindset that seeks to align agricultural practices with broader environmental goals.

These archetypes highlight the range in attitudes and motivations among farmers in Guadalajara, reflecting a complex interplay of economic, social, and environmental factors. Understanding these differences is crucial for developing targeted interventions that can effectively promote soil conservation across various farmer profiles.

What challenges prevent farmers from adopting practices that favour soil health?

Several challenges hinder the adoption of soil protection practices, particularly among farmers who prioritize short-term economic gains. Economic pressure is a significant barrier, as many farmers operate on thin margins and cannot afford to experiment with new practices that may not offer immediate returns. The uncertainty of financial outcomes associated with sustainable practices, such as reduced tillage or cover cropping, further discourages their adoption (Knowler & Bradshaw, 2007; Läßle & Rensburg, 2011).

There is a general skepticism toward external advice and a preference for self-reliance. Many farmers trust their own experience over recommendations from research or advisory services. This skepticism is often reinforced by a sense of alienation from society, where farmers feel misunderstood or unfairly judged by the public and policymakers. This disconnect can make them less open to adopting new practices.

Bureaucratic obstacles also play a significant role in hindering the adoption of sustainable practices. The complexity and perceived unfairness of subsidy systems, particularly those linked to the CAP, are sources of frustration. Farmers expressed a preference for "compensation payments" tied to fair market prices rather than traditional subsidies, which they view as overly restrictive and not reflective of the true value of their work. The burden of paperwork and compliance with regulations further discourages participation in programs that could promote soil health (Defrancesco *et al.*, 2007). Lastly, a lack of clear succession plans and the uncertainty about the future of their farms seem to reduce the incentive for long-term investments in soil conservation.

What conclusions can be drawn regarding current policy measures and how can they be improved to better support sustainable practices?

The current policy measures, particularly those related to the CAP, are often seen as inadequate in addressing the real needs of farmers. The one-size-fits-all approach of the CAP fails to account for the diverse realities of European farmers, especially those in regions like Guadalajara, where environmental and economic conditions are challenging.

To improve the effectiveness of policy measures, a wider approach is needed. Expanding AES and making them more accessible and relevant to farmers could encourage greater participation. These schemes should be designed to offer tangible benefits, both economic and ecological, to make sustainable practices more attractive. Additionally, reducing the bureaucratic burden associated with these programs

and simplifying the application processes could increase farmer engagement. Policymakers need to engage more directly with farmers to understand their concerns and priorities. This dialogue should aim to bridge the gap between societal expectations and the realities of farming. There is a need to rethink the way subsidies are distributed. Shifting from traditional subsidies to compensation payments linked to fair product prices could help address some of the economic challenges farmers face. Such an approach would have to recognize the value of sustainable practices and provide farmers with the financial stability needed to invest in soil health.

This work raises several important questions for future research. One key area for further exploration is how to effectively engage farmers who prioritize short-term economic gains over long-term sustainability. Understanding the specific economic pressures these farmers face and identifying strategies that can make sustainable practices more economically viable for them is essential. Another important question is how to bridge the gap between farmers and society. Building a more supportive relationship between these groups could enhance the acceptance of sustainable practices and reduce the sense of alienation that many farmers feel. Future research could explore the role of education and communication in fostering a better understanding of the challenges farmers face and the importance of soil conservation.

The insights gained here are not only relevant for Guadalajara but also have broader implications for agricultural policy in other regions facing similar issues. By addressing the diverse needs and priorities of farmers, policymakers can create a more sustainable future for agriculture and ensure the long-term health and productivity of our soils.

8. References

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Declaration of the use of generative AI tools

Throughout my research, I employed generative AI tools such as ChatGPT for drafting and revising text, and specialized software for data analysis and visualization. These tools were used to enhance the efficiency and depth of analysis within the thesis. The AI tools were utilized to assist in the synthesis of large volumes of literature, provide preliminary data interpretations, and generate graphical representations of data (eg. LitMaps), thereby augmenting the research process. These tools were applied primarily in the literature review, data analysis, and editing phases of the thesis. Human oversight was maintained throughout, ensuring that all outputs were critically evaluated and validated for accuracy and relevance. The following table provides a detailed list of which AI tools were used, to what extent, and for which activities.

Activity	Tools used	Description of the tool usage
Literature search	ChatGPT (Consensus), Perplexity, LitMaps	Relevant literature was partly found with the help of AI. <i>LitMaps</i> simplified the snowball system for literature. Literature found with the help of AI can be located in all chapters of this thesis.
Interpretation	ChatGPT, PDF AI, Perplexity	For a quick examination of the literature, the first step of interpretation was carried out with the help of AI. With the help of <i>PDF AI</i> and <i>Perplexity</i> , I was able to quickly find suitable passages in the literature. this literature can be found in all chapters. Primary in chapters 1,2,3,6.
Structuring and planning the text	ChatGPT	<i>ChatGPT</i> was used for structuring inspiration. This concerns the structure of the entire work. However, it is based on the classic structure of a scientific thesis.
Generating text	ChatGPT, GoodTape	The transcription of the interviews was simplified with the help of <i>GoodTape</i> . Some text passages were inserted into <i>ChatGPT</i> to link them together. Inspiration and ideas (such as for the title) were generated using <i>ChatGPT</i> .
Translating text	DeepL, Google translate, ChatGPT	To translate literature from English to German for a better understanding. To translate interviews from Spanish to German and English. To translate text passages written by me in German or Spanish into English. Translation tools were used throughout this thesis.
Reviewing & editing the text	ChatGPT, DeepL Write, Word Editor	<i>ChatGPT</i> was sometimes used for grammatical correction. Word, with its editor, also helped. <i>DeepL Write</i> was used to find synonyms for individual words, or to make certain sentences sound better. These tools were used throughout this thesis.

Citation Management	Zotero	With the help of <i>Zotero</i> , the citations were formatted, and a reference list was created.
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I acknowledge the contributions of the generative AI tools in handling data-heavy tasks and supporting decision-making processes. However, the final analysis, interpretation, and scholarly writing were conducted by myself, under the guidance of my thesis advisor. The ethical guidelines from the University of Lifescience (Vienna) were strictly followed in the deployment of AI tools, ensuring transparency, fairness, and respect for intellectual property rights. All AI-generated content was appropriately inspected and modified by human intelligence.

I hereby declare that generative AI tools were used responsibly in the preparation of this thesis and that all outputs were subject to rigorous scrutiny to uphold the integrity of the research.

Vienna, 13.09.2024

Ernesto Jose LUNAR KOCH

List of Abbreviation

AES	Agri-Environmental Schemes
APAG	Asociación Provincial de Agricultores y Ganaderos
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
EAGF	European Agricultural Guarantee Fund
EAGFRG	European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development
EU	European Union
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GF	Good Farmer
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
LSU	Livestock Unit
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
UAA	Utilised Agricultural Area
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention for Climate Change

List of Figures

Figure 1: Spanish Budget allocation to interventions in Pillar 1 and Pillar 2, in million euros	9
Figure 2: Levels of different factors that affect the implementation of sustainable practices. Based on Dessart et al. (2019)	16
Figure 3: Superordinate sentence and exemplary statements.	22
Figure 4: Forced choice distribution of the Q-Sort	26
Figure 5: Temperature in degree Celsius of Guadalajara in April of 2022 and April of 2023 reported by hour, color-coded in bands. On the Y-Axis the hours of the day are shown, while the X-Axis present the day. (Weather Spark, n.d.).....	31
Figure 6: Composite Q-Sort for Factor 1 “ <i>The soil considered</i> ”	43
Figure 7: Composite Q-Sort for Factor 2 “ <i>The economic individualist</i> ”	45
Figure 8: Composite Q-Sort for Factor 3 “ <i>The contemporary-minded</i> ”	47

List of Tables

Table 1: Climatic parameters from Guadalajara 1989-2010; T: Monthly/annual mean temperature (°C) , TM: Monthly/annual mean daily maximum temperatures (°C), Tm: monthly/annual mean daily minimum temperatures (°C), R: Monthly/annual mean precipitation (mm). (Agencia Estatal de Metereologia, n.d.)	12
Table 2: The Q-set contains 45 statements. The statements are numbered and listed according to their category. All of the statements refer to the opening sentence.	23
Table 3: Respondents' characteristics for the full sample and by factor (F1-F3).....	32
Table 4: Soil management practices applied by participants are categorized into archetypes resulting from Q-analysis. Specifically, F1 corresponds to the „ <i>The soil considered</i> ”, F2 to the “ <i>The economic individualist</i> ”, and F3 to “ <i>The contemporary-minded</i> ”.	33
Table 5: Correlation Matrix of the three rotated factors	34
Table 6: This table presents the factor loadings of Q-Sorts, highlighting in bold those sorts that significantly define the factors ($p > 0.05$). The table also includes the number of defining Q-Sorts for each factor, the percentage of explained variance, and Eigenvalues.....	34
Table 7: List of statements and factor scores. Consensus statements that do not differ significantly between any pair of factors are marked with an asterisk.	36
Table 8: Consensus statements that, at a significance level of $p < 0.05$, do not exhibit significant differences between at least two factors.	38
Table 9: Distinguishing statements at $p < 0.05$ (bold = $p < 0.01$).....	39

Appendix A: Spanish Statements

No.	Declaración
	Cuando trabajo con mi tierra, es importante para mí...
1	... Ver que mis parcelas parezcan ordenadas y limpias.
2	... preservar el suelo para las generaciones futuras.
3	... considerar los costes incurridos.
4	... garantizar la viabilidad económica de mi explotación a largo plazo.
5	... obtener ganancias con ello en este año.
6	... recibir subsidios por mi actividad.
7	... maximizar los rendimientos de los cultivos en este año.
8	... cómo de lejos está una explotación de su edificación.
9	... entregarla a mis sucesores en buenas condiciones.
10	... que se pueda trabajar con la maquinaria de que dispongo.
11	... ser dueño de la parcela.
12	... confiar en lo que aprendí en mi formación o educación.
13	... confiar en las experiencias de los colegas.
14	... confiar en mis propias experiencias prácticas.
15	... hacer aquello en lo que creo.
16	... considerar cómo se cultivan las parcelas vecinas.
17	... considerar cómo afectan mis acciones a mis vecinos.
18	... minimizar el tiempo de trabajo.
19	... confiar en el conocimiento tradicional y transmitido.
20	... contar con el asesoramiento de los servicios de consultoría.
21	... cuánto tiempo continuaré trabajando el suelo.
22	... que no tenga que lidiar con más papeleo del necesario.
23	... confiar en los últimos resultados de investigación o en las recomendaciones.
24	... no entrar en conflicto con las regulaciones legales.
25	... mitigar los efectos negativos de los fenómenos meteorológicos extremos.
26	... reducir la erosión del suelo.
27	... prevenir plagas.
28	... conocer los datos de calidad del suelo de la parcela.

- 29 ... cumplir con los requisitos de mis compradores.
 - 30 ... satisfacer las expectativas de la sociedad.
 - 31 ... producir alimentos para la sociedad.
 - 32 ... ver que mis acciones tienen un impacto positivo en el medio ambiente.
 - 33 ... trabajar junto con la naturaleza.
 - 34 ...ver cómo mis acciones afectan a los organismos del suelo, como las lombrices de tierra.
 - 35 ... no convertirme en objeto de habladurías.
 - 36 ... que el trabajo me satisfaga.
 - 37 ... evitar riesgos económicos.
 - 38 ... garantizar un rendimiento estable.
 - 39 ... probar nuevas prácticas.
 - 40 ... incrementar el carbono orgánico del suelo.
 - 41 ... evitar la pérdida de nutrientes.
 - 42 ... minimizar el uso de maquinaria.
 - 43 ... para proteger los recursos de agua.
 - 44 ...que tenga en cuenta los cambios climáticos.
 - 45 ...aumentar la capacidad de retención de agua del suelo.
-

Appendix B: Questionnaire (Spanish)

Datos de la entrevista: Location:, Fecha:, Hora:

Año de nacimiento:	Sexo	<input type="checkbox"/> masculino	<input type="checkbox"/> mujer	<input type="checkbox"/> otros	<input type="checkbox"/> n.d.
Formación más avanzada	<input type="checkbox"/> Sin formación	<input type="checkbox"/> Escuela bachillerato; aprendizaje	sin <input type="checkbox"/> Escuela con <input type="checkbox"/> Escuela bachillerat o; máster	<input type="checkbox"/> Título universitario	<input type="checkbox"/> n.d.
Responsable de operaciones desde:	<input type="checkbox"/> <5 Años	<input type="checkbox"/> 5-14 Años	<input type="checkbox"/> 15-30 Años	<input type="checkbox"/> >30 Años	<input type="checkbox"/> kn.d.

Betriebsmerkmale

Tamaño de la explotación (ha), sin de las cuales de las cuales
bosque: Tierra cultivable (ha): superficie arrendada (ha):

Modo de funcionamiento (principalmente)

<input type="checkbox"/> Cultivos	<input type="checkbox"/> Horticultura	<input type="checkbox"/> Cultura	<input type="checkbox"/> Ganado de permanente pastoreo	<input type="checkbox"/> Cerdos / <input type="checkbox"/> Mixto Aves de corral
-----------------------------------	---------------------------------------	----------------------------------	---	--

Ganado (UGM o número):

Número de cultivos en su rotación típica Ecológico: Si No Parcial

Medidas agroambientales (en caso afirmativo, ¿cuáles?):

Actividad agrícola principal Actividad agrícola secundaria

Labranza: ¿Cuál de las siguientes prácticas de labranza utiliza?

	toda la empresa	parcialmente	para nada	n.d.
Enverdecimiento	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Subsiembra	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Arado	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Labranza reducida	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Labranza sin arado / siembra directa	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fertilizante mineral	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Abono líquido / purín / estiércol	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Compost	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Biocarbón	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Estudios del suelo	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Otros:	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

¿Qué cree que hace bueno a un agricultor?

	No estoy de acuerdo					Estoy de acuerdo					
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	n.d.
Un buen granjero...											
...tiene campos limpios	<input type="checkbox"/>										
...no tiene malas hierbas en los campos	<input type="checkbox"/>										
...tiene líneas rectas en los campos	<input type="checkbox"/>										
...genera altos rendimientos	<input type="checkbox"/>										
...tiene una rotación de cultivos diversificada	<input type="checkbox"/>										

...utiliza vegetación	<input type="checkbox"/>					
...presta atención a la biodiversidad	<input type="checkbox"/>					
...tiene grandes máquinas	<input type="checkbox"/>					
... ara sus campos	<input type="checkbox"/>					
...utiliza labranza reducida	<input type="checkbox"/>					
... trabaja de manera ecológica	<input type="checkbox"/>					
... trabaja convencionalmente	<input type="checkbox"/>					
...utiliza la labranza de conservación	<input type="checkbox"/>					
...utiliza la agricultura regenerativa	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Appendix C: Consent Form (Spanish)

Universidad de Recursos Naturales y Ciencias de la Vida de Viena

Información sobre el tratamiento de datos personales en el marco de una entrevista

A partir del 25 de mayo de 2018, el Reglamento del Parlamento Europeo y del Consejo de 27 de abril de 2016, relativo a la protección de las personas físicas en lo que respecta al tratamiento de datos personales y a la libre circulación de estos datos y por el que se deroga la Directiva 95/46/CE (Reglamento General de Protección de Datos (RGPD)) es directamente aplicable en todos los Estados miembros de la Unión Europea.

Entre otras cosas, el RGPD establece obligaciones de información ampliadas en relación con el tratamiento de datos personales.

En cumplimiento de estas obligaciones (en particular del artículo 13 del RGPD), le informamos por la presente sobre el (los) tratamiento(s) de sus datos personales que llevamos a cabo.

1. ¿Qué datos personales ("datos" para abreviar) se tratan?

Se tratan los datos solicitados en la entrevista y facilitados voluntariamente por Ud.

2. ¿Con qué fin se tratan los datos?

Los datos recogidos en la entrevista se tratarán en el marco del proyecto de investigación SoilX exclusivamente con fines de investigación.

Si desea recibir los resultados de la investigación, sus datos de contacto (nombre, dirección postal o dirección de correo electrónico) también se tratarán con el fin de enviárselos.

3. ¿Con qué fundamento jurídico se tratan los datos?

No tiene obligación de participar en la entrevista. La comunicación de sus datos es voluntaria. Sus datos serán tratados sobre la base de su consentimiento dado durante la entrevista para los fines mencionados.

Puede revocar su consentimiento en cualquier momento con efectos para el futuro, sin ninguna consecuencia negativa para Ud. Una revocación tiene como consecuencia que, a partir de ese momento, dejaremos de tratar sus datos para la finalidad mencionada y, en particular, que suprimiremos los datos (todavía) almacenados.

4. ¿Se transfieren total o parcialmente los datos a otras personas/ entidades?

No
 Sí, sus datos serán transferidos a los siguientes destinatarios en el curso del tratamiento para la finalidad mencionada:

5. ¿Están situados los destinatarios mencionados en el punto 4 fuera de la UE/ el EEE o se trata de una organización internacional?

No

 Sí, en concreto:

El destinatario	País tercero	Organización internacional	Nivel de protección (artículo según el RGPD)
			<input type="checkbox"/> Decisión de adecuación de la Comisión Europea con arreglo al art. 45 <input type="checkbox"/> Normas internas vinculantes de protección de datos con arreglo al art. 47, junto con el art. 46, apartado 2, letra b) <input type="checkbox"/> Cláusulas estándar de protección de datos con arreglo al art. 46, apartado 2, letras c) y d) <input type="checkbox"/> Normas de conducta aprobadas con arreglo al art. 46, apartado 2, letra e), junto con el art. 40 <input type="checkbox"/> Mecanismo de certificación aprobado con arreglo al art. 46, apartado 2, letra f), junto con el art. 42 <input type="checkbox"/> Cláusulas contractuales aprobadas por la autoridad de protección de datos con arreglo al art. 46, apartado 3, letra a). <input type="checkbox"/> Excepción para caso concreto con arreglo al art. 49, apartado 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Excepción para caso concreto con arreglo al art. 49, apartado 1, subapartado 2

6. ¿Cuánto tiempo se almacenan los datos o qué criterios se utilizan para determinar la duración del almacenamiento?

Las grabaciones de audio de las entrevistas se borrarán a más tardar un mes después de su transcripción y seudonimización.

Las transcripciones seudonimizadas y otros datos no relacionables personalmente se conservarán mientras dure el proyecto de investigación y más allá con el fin de archivar los datos de la investigación, así como para investigaciones posteriores.

Los datos de contacto para el envío de resultados se conservarán hasta que se hayan enviado los resultados (hasta un máximo de 1 año después del final del proyecto de investigación) y después se eliminarán.

Otros datos (por ejemplo, claves para la seudonimización) se almacenan en el marco de las obligaciones legales de conservación.

7. ¿Qué derechos tiene usted como interesado(a)?

Por lo general, le asisten los derechos de información, rectificación, borrado, limitación, portabilidad de datos y revocación.

Para ejercer estos derechos, póngase en contacto con nuestro(a) encargado(a) de protección de datos (para los datos de contacto, véase el punto 8).

Además, tiene derecho a presentar cualquier reclamación ante la autoridad de protección de datos.

8. Datos de contacto

- **Responsable**
Universidad de Recursos Naturales y Ciencias de la Vida de Viena
Gregor-Mendel-Straße 33
1180 Viena
- **Encargado(a) de protección de datos**
Muthgasse 11/II
1190 Viena
datenschutz@boku.ac.at

Encontrará información general y más detallada sobre el tema de la protección de datos en la Universidad de Recursos Naturales y Ciencias Aplicadas de la Vida de Viena en la dirección siguiente www.boku.ac.at/datenschutz.

Appendix D: General Participants Information sheet (englisch)

Information about the research project SoilX in [country]

Looking for farmer interview participants in the [region]

What is this research project about?

Soil and its management provide the basis for farming and are integral parts of the work of farmers. In light of increasing pressure on soils from climate change, soil sealing, and intensification of agriculture maintaining soil health has become a focus of agricultural policy. At the same time, farmers face many decisions when working their soil, and because each piece of land, each farm, and each farmer are different, the **perspectives on what is important in soil management** differ greatly among them.

The research project SoilX (Soil management to mitigate climate change-related precipitation extremes) is funded by the European Commission and takes place in six countries from 2022-2024. The research team at [project partner] is lead by:

[contact information]

These different perspectives of farmers are at the core of the ongoing research project SoilX. The project aims to **generate better scientific knowledge** in: 1) how soil properties (such as water retention capacity or soil organic carbon) change depending on soil management practices and climatic changes; and 2) **which factors are most important to farmers** when they consider their **soil management options**. While soil scientists are addressing the first goal using soil testing and scenario modelling, we from [project partner] are working on the second goal.

What are we looking for?

To address this second goal in the [country] context, we are looking for farmers from the [region] who are willing to take **share their practical farming knowledge and opinion** in a **guided, face-to-face, conversation** with our research team. The conversation will focus on participants' farm, what is important to them in their soil management, and in their farming in general. We will also ask participants to reflect on a set of statements about farming as part of a method that involves sorting a set of cards. This sorting exercise will allow us to compare the views of different farmers to one another.

Participants **do not need to prepare anything** but just share their **personal experience**. The conversation can take place anywhere that is convenient to participants and where there is some space e.g., on a table, for the sorting exercise. We will ask participants whether we may audio-record the conversation to ease analysis.

In short, we are looking for **30 farmers** to participate in interviews taking approx. **1 hour** and who

- Farm some **cropland** in the [region]
- Are farming part-time **or** full-time; **any** farm size
- Farm mixed farms **or** crop farms; conventional **or** organic;
- Do **or** do not apply soil management practices such as reduced tilling, no-till, cover cropping, etc.

What will happen with research results?

Research **results will be made available to participants** and the general public. We will (1) present and discuss results with interested participants and other stakeholders in an in-person **workshop** next winter; (2) provide a research result summary to participants at the end of the project in 2024; and (3) prepare scientific publications in international scientific journals.

What's in it for participants?

Participation in this research project is **voluntary**. If you decide to participate, we can unfortunately not remunerate you for your time and effort, but there are several other potential benefits:

- By participating, you contribute to a **better understanding of farmers' motivations** and the challenges they face in soil management by **scientists** and **policy** makers, which may improve future soil-related policies.
- You can get **first-hand insights into research outcomes**, including the soil testing and scenario modelling results based on soil management experiments in [region], and interview results.
- We will also **invite you** to learn about and discuss these research results in a voluntary **follow-up workshop** with other farmers and stakeholders. There you will again have the opportunity to contribute to improving research insights and make sure farmers' knowledge and interests are represented well in the process.

What will happen with the information and data you share with us?

All personal data will be used for scientific research within the project only. Anything you share with us will be treated as **highly confidential** and not be shared with anyone outside the research team.

For data analysis and the preparation of research results, the information you shared with us will be **anonymised** such that it is **impossible to identify you or your farm personally**. To do so, we will take the following steps:

- Information shared in the conversation: Given your consent, we will audio-record the interviews and then transcribed them into written text. This text will be stripped of any information that could directly identify you or others mentioned (e.g., names, addresses) and given an **anonymous ID** for all further analysis. We then **delete** the original audio-recording.
- The outcome of the sorting exercise: we will take a picture of the sorting outcome that will be digitized and stored under the same anonymous ID as the transcribed text.
- General information about the farm and yourself (e.g., farm type, farm size, your farming education): We will anonymise and store this information using the anonymous ID and if necessary by coarsening information content (e.g., by turning exact farm size information into size classes).
- All data will be stored in a **protected** way (encrypted files; locked) and any identifying data will be deleted after the end of the project (except where we are legally obliged to store information, e.g., to be able to delete your information if you ask us to).
- If you wish to receive research results or are interested in joining a **results discussion workshop**, we will also store your contact data for this purpose only.
- The signed consent and data protection forms (see next page) will be stored in a locked place at [project partner].

Completely anonymous data that is not traceable to a single person will be **archived** for reference as well as for potential future analysis.

What if I change my mind about participation or if I have concerns about the research?

If you have any questions, concerns, or complaints about this research project, you can contact **XY** (see contact details above) or **XY** at any time.

Even if you agree to participate in this research project right now, you can ask us any time to delete all the information you shared with us or not use it for any (future) research. To do so, contact **XY**

Are there any formalities?

At the interview we will ask you to sign a document to confirm that you participate voluntarily in the interview, that you have been informed about the project and how we will use your data, and that we may process your data in accordance with legislation. Enclosed you can find this document for your review.

Declaration of consent for research project SoilX

It is important to us that we conduct all our research in such a way that all participants are fully informed about what their participation in the project entails, and provide their voluntary consent to their participation.

In addition, the [project partner] takes the protection of personal data seriously. We consider the protection of privacy in the processing of personal data an important issue, to which we pay great attention in our processes.

The processing of your personal data in accordance with the enclosed "Information on the processing of personal data for interviews" only takes place with your voluntary consent.

Please carefully review the following and confirm your consent:

- I confirm that my participation in this research is **voluntary** and that I can withdraw from it at any time (e.g., interrupt the interview; ask researchers not to use my data)
- I confirm that I have **received information** about the research project and that I had the opportunity to ask questions about it that have been answered satisfactorily
- I confirm that the interview will be **audio-recorded** for analysis, and that audio recordings will be deleted after transcription into pseudonymized text
- I have understood how my **data will be used** (see enclosed form on the processing of personal data for interviews) and what my rights as a data subject are
- I agree that the [project partner] will process my personal data in accordance with the enclosed form on the processing of personal data for interviews

Name:

Place, date:

Signature:

Appendix E: Participants Information sheet (Spain Version)

Búsqueda de participantes para entrevistas con agricultores en España Central (Guadalajara)

Información sobre el proyecto de investigación SoilX en España

Entrevistas sobre el cultivo del suelo

Como parte del proyecto del proyecto "SoilX", estamos investigando las **decisiones que toman las agricultoras y los agricultores** a la hora de elegir sus métodos de cultivo del suelo.

¿Cultivas al menos una parcela en el centro de España (**Guadalajara**)? ¿Le gustaría compartir su experiencia con nosotros y apoyar la investigación del suelo? Póngase en contacto con nosotros para participar en una entrevista de **aproximadamente una hora**. Estaremos encantados de visitarle en su finca.

Contacto para la participación:

Ernesto José Lunar Koch
E-Mail: e.lunar-koch@students.boku.ac.at
Tel.: +34 675 985 677

Información detallada

¿En qué consiste este proyecto de investigación?

El **suelo y su gestión** son la base de la agricultura y del trabajo de los agricultores. A la luz de la creciente presión sobre los suelos a causa del cambio climático, el sellado del suelo y la intensificación de la agricultura el mantenimiento de la salud del suelo se ha convertido en uno de los principales focos de la política agrícola. Al mismo tiempo, los agricultores deben hacer frente a numerosas decisiones a la hora de trabajar el suelo, en parte debido a que cada pedazo de tierra, cada explotación y cada agricultor es diferente. Las **perspectivas sobre lo realmente importante en la gestión del suelo** difieren mucho.

Estas diferentes perspectivas de los agricultores son el objeto del proyecto SoilX, del programa EJP Soil. Este proyecto está financiado por la Comisión Europea y se desarrolla entre 2022 y 2024 en seis países. El objetivo del proyecto general es **obtener mejores conocimientos** científicos sobre tres cuestiones de investigación:

- 1) ¿Cómo cambian las propiedades físicas del suelo en función del método de laboreo?
- 2) ¿En qué medida pueden contribuir estos cambios a reducir los riesgos climáticos, como el aumento de las sequías o las precipitaciones intensas?
- 3) ¿Qué factores son los más importantes para los agricultores a la hora de considerar sus opciones de cultivo?

Para responder a las dos primeras preguntas, realizamos observaciones en terrenos experimentales repartidos por toda Europa. La segunda pregunta se estudia a partir de pronósticos climáticos con ayuda de modelos. La respuesta **a la tercera pregunta es el objeto de este estudio**. En el Instituto de Desarrollo Económico Sostenible de la Universidad BOKU (Viena) nos encargamos de este tema y tratamos de hablar con los agricultores al respecto. El equipo de investigación del BOKU está dirigido por la Dra. Heidi Leonhardt (contacto: heidi.leonhardt@boku.ac.at o +43 1 47654-73100) con la ayuda de Inés Santín y Marta Goberna Estellés de INIA.

¿Qué buscamos?

Buscamos agricultores que les apetezca **compartir su opinión y sus conocimientos prácticos** sobre manejo agrícola en una **conversación informal** con nuestro equipo. La conversación se centrará en la experiencia de los participantes, para que conozcamos mejor cómo manejan sus cultivos y su terreno en general, y cuáles son las dificultades que encuentran en su día a día. También les pediremos su opinión sobre una serie de declaraciones sobre la agricultura para entender qué consideran un buen manejo agrícola, lo que nos permitirá comparar las opiniones (anonimizadas) de diferentes agricultores.

Los participantes **no necesitan preparar nada**, simplemente charlarán sobre su **experiencia personal**. La conversación puede tener lugar en cualquier lugar que resulte conveniente para los participantes y donde exista algo de espacio, como una mesa, para poder realizar el ejercicio de clasificación de las tarjetas. Preguntaremos a los participantes si podemos grabar la conversación (solo audio) para facilitar a los investigadores el recordar las respuestas de cada miembro (ver detalles abajo sobre el manejo de las grabaciones). Por supuesto, la grabación es totalmente voluntaria y no hay ningún problema si un participante no quiere ser grabado.

En resumen, estamos buscando a **30 agricultores** para participar en entrevistas de **1 hora** aprox. y que:

- Explote al menos una **parcela de tierra cultivable**
- Cultiven a tiempo parcial o a jornada completa una explotación agrícola de **cualquier** tamaño;
- **No existen requisitos específicos** para los métodos de gestión del suelo (arado, siembra directa, revegetación, etc.).

¿Y para los participantes?

La participación en este proyecto de investigación es **voluntaria**. Si decide participar, lamentablemente no podremos remunerarle por su tiempo y dedicación, pero sí existen otros posibles beneficios para usted:

Al participar, usted contribuye a **una mejor comprensión de las motivaciones de los agricultores**, así como de los desafíos a los que deben hacer frente los **científicos** y los responsables políticos en la gestión del suelo. Estos conocimientos pueden mejorar las futuras políticas relacionadas con el suelo.

- Puede obtener **información de primera mano sobre los resultados de la investigación**, incluyendo los resultados de las pruebas de suelo y el modelado de escenarios en base a experimentos de manejo del terreno en España Central (Guadalajara) y a los resultados de las entrevistas.

¿Qué pasará con los resultados de la investigación?

Los **resultados de la investigación se pondrán a disposición de los participantes** y el público en general, siempre respetando el anonimato de los participantes (ver explicación abajo).

- (1) presentaremos y discutiremos personalmente los resultados con los participantes y otras partes interesadas como universidades europeas e instituciones de política agrícola.
- (2) se ofrecerá un resumen de los resultados de la investigación a los participantes al final del proyecto en 2024; y
- (3) se realizarán publicaciones en revistas científicas internacionales.

Para más información sobre protección de datos, ir a la **página siguiente**.

¿Qué pasará con la información y los datos que comparta con nosotros?

Todos los datos personales se utilizarán únicamente para **investigación científica** dentro del proyecto. Cualquier información compartida con nosotros será tratada como altamente confidencial y no se compartirá con nadie fuera del equipo de investigación.

Para el análisis de los datos y la elaboración de los resultados de la investigación, la información compartida con nosotros será **anónima** de modo que resulte **imposible identificarle a usted o a su explotación**. Para ello, seguiremos los siguientes pasos:

- Información compartida en la conversación: con su consentimiento, grabaremos las entrevistas y luego las transcribiremos en texto escrito. Este texto omitirá cualquier dato que pueda identificarlo directamente a usted o a otras personas mencionadas (nombres, direcciones, etc.) y será **identificado de forma anónima** para todos los análisis posteriores. Luego **eliminaremos** la grabación de audio original.
- El resultado del ejercicio de clasificación de tarjetas: realizaremos una foto del resultado de la clasificación que será digitalizada y almacenada bajo la misma identificación anónima que aparece el texto transcrito.
- Información general sobre la explotación y sobre usted (tipo de cultivo, tamaño de la explotación, su formación agrícola): anonimizaremos y almacenaremos esta información utilizando una identificación anónima
- Todos los datos se almacenan de manera **protegida** (archivos encriptados; bloqueo) y cualquier dato identificativo se eliminará una vez finalizado el proyecto (excepto cuando estemos legalmente obligados a almacenar información, por ejemplo, para poder eliminar sus datos si nos lo solicita).
- Si desea recibir resultados de la investigación o está interesado en participar en un **taller de debate sobre los resultados**, también almacenaremos sus datos de contacto solo para este propósito.

Los datos completamente anónimos que no se pueden asociar a una persona se conservan como referencia para posibles análisis en el futuro.

¿Qué pasa si cambio de opinión sobre la participación o si tengo cualquier duda sobre la investigación?

Si tiene alguna pregunta, duda o queja sobre este proyecto de investigación, no dude en ponerse en contacto con Ernesto José Lunar Koch e.lunar-koch@students.boku.ac.at (Tel.: +43 681 10210793).

¿Existe alguna formalidad?

En la entrevista le pediremos que firme un documento para confirmar que participa voluntariamente en la entrevista, que ha sido informado sobre el proyecto y la forma en la que utilizaremos sus datos, además de que podemos procesar sus datos de acuerdo con la legislación vigente. Puede encontrar adjunto este documento para su revisión.

Appendix F: Interview Protocol (Spanish)

Entrevistas a agricultores de SoilX y Metodología Q

INTRODUCCIÓN

- *Bienvenido, Gracias*
- *Breve información sobre el proyecto de investigación*
- *Protección de datos y consentimiento para participar ¡Firma!*
- *Encienda el dispositivo de grabación.*

CALENTAMIENTO Y PREGUNTAS DE PREPARACIÓN

Tema	Posibles preguntas de seguimiento	Posibles aspectos de interés
Explotación	<p>¿Podría presentarme brevemente su Explotación?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • - ¿Qué tamaño tiene su Explotación? (¿Qué ganadería?) • - ¿Cuáles son los cultivos principales? • - ¿Cómo vende sus productos? • - ¿En qué medida diría que su explotación es típica de la zona? • - ¿Quién participa en las decisiones agrícolas? 	Tipo de Explotación , Explotación familiar, Cultivos principales, comercialización directa/cliente, Especificidades de la Explotación
Agricultor/a	<p>¿Podría contarme algo sobre usted y su función en la Explotación?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • - ¿Cómo llegó a administrar esta Explotación? • - ¿Cuánto tiempo lleva aquí como jefe de la granja? (caso de serlo) • - ¿Qué educación agrícola tiene? 	Experiencia en la Explotación , Empresa familiar, Educación
Condiciones de cultivo	<p>¿Podría darme información básica sobre las condiciones de cultivo de su explotación, especialmente sobre los cultivos herbáceos?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • - ¿Cómo es el suelo aquí? • - ¿En qué medida hay zonas montañosas o con riesgo de erosión en su explotación? • - ¿Cuáles son los retos meteorológicos? ¿Ha cambiado algo en los últimos años? • - ¿En qué medida sus tierras está en una única superficie o en varias fragmentadas? 	Calidad o tipo de suelo, topografía, Condiciones climáticas, el cambio climático, fragmentación de las superficies

Cultivo del suelo	<p>¿Podría describirme su estrategia de manejo del suelo? ¿En qué medida ha cambiado su sistema de trabajo desde que es agricultor aquí?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ¿Hubo algún motivo o factor especial que lo provocó? • ¿Recibe subvenciones para ciertas medidas? 	Adaptación al cambio climático, (clima extremo) eventos, Subvención
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Q METHODE: SORTIEREN

Ahora tenemos un pequeño ejercicio para ti. Hemos traído unas tarjetas con frases relacionadas con tu trabajo con el suelo. Se trata de tu propia opinión y de lo que tú **personalmente** consideras importante, así que **no hay "correcto" o "incorrecto"**, sólo tu juicio sobre tu propia situación.

Ahora les entrego estas pequeñas tarjetas y les pido en primero:

- **Lea** cada tarjeta (*¡ofrézcase a leerla en voz alta a los agricultores si tiene problemas para leer!*)
- Para cada frase, decida **espontáneamente** si está de **acuerdo**, en **desacuerdo** o **no tiene opinión** sobre la frase.
- Coloca las tarjetas según corresponda en **tres montones**: "de acuerdo", "en desacuerdo" y "me da igual".

Siguiente

- Coge sólo el **montón de los que están "de acuerdo"** y busca las frases con las que estás **más de acuerdo**, es decir, las que son más importantes para ti, y clasifícalas en la tabla preparada en el extremo **derecho**.
- Busca las frases con las que estés más de acuerdo y clasifícalas junto a las más importantes, etc.

Siguiente

- Haz lo mismo con el montón de tarjetas **"en desacuerdo"** e identifica aquellas con las que estés más en desacuerdo y ordénalas en el extremo **izquierdo** de la tabla.
- Por último, por favor, ordene las frases "me da igual" en el centro de la tabla.

Finalmente

- Vuelve a mirar el cuadro tabla con tranquilidad. ¿Tiene sentido para ti? **También puede cambiar algo**.

MÉTODO Q: REFLEXIÓN

- Si consideramos las cartas del extremo derecho, ¿podría explicarme **por qué decidió colocarlas ahí?**
- Cuando **leyó por primera vez** esta frase, ¿qué le vino a la mente? ¿Qué significa para ti **[tema de la tarjeta]**.
- ...lo mismo para el extremo izquierdo...

- - ¿Qué tarjetas le han parecido **más difíciles** de clasificar? ¿**Por qué?**
- ¿Hay algún tema importante que eche en falta? ¿Hay alguna tarjeta que deberíamos haber preparado?
- ¿En qué pensaste cuando leíste "**trabaja con tu suelo**"? ¿Qué actividades, aspectos, consideraciones, sentimientos?

BUEN AGRICULTOR

Ahora me gustaría preguntarle algunas cosas sobre cómo se considera a sí mismo y a los demás agricultores. Como seres humanos, es probablemente importante que todos nos sintamos lo bastante bien tanto en privado como en nuestro trabajo. Por eso, me gustaría hacerle algunas preguntas sobre lo que puede significar ser un "buen" agricultor desde su perspectiva.

Tema	Preguntas de orientación y continuación
Buen Agricultor	<p>Cuando piensa en esta región, ¿cómo describiría a alguien que es un "buen agricultor"?</p> <p>¿Cómo reconocerías a un buen agricultor basándote en el aspecto de su explotación?</p>
Mal Agricultor	<p>¿Y cómo describiría a alguien que es un mal agricultor?</p> <p>¿Cómo reconocer a un mal agricultor?</p>
Cambios	<p>¿Ha cambiado su opinión sobre lo que debe hacer un buen agricultor desde que empezó a trabajar como agricultor?</p> <p>En caso de que sí, ¿de qué manera?</p>

CUESTIONARIO Y CONCLUSIÓN

*Pedir que se rellene **el formulario con datos demográficos / información general***

Gracias, creo que esta es toda la información que necesitamos. Gracias de nuevo por su tiempo.

Quizás desee mencionar o discutir aquí otros temas:

- - Sugerencias para otros participantes de las entrevistas

- - Talleres con las partes interesadas y presentación de los resultados el próximo invierno: ¿Le interesa?
- - ¿Le interesa recibir los resultados (pueden tardar unos meses)?
- - Recuerde de nuevo a los participantes que pueden ponerse en contacto con nosotros en cualquier momento si tienen preguntas o dudas.